

Shared innovations and the “Tangut-Horpa clade”: A demonstration of Neogrammarian principles in language classification*

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Abstract

This paper conducts a comprehensive exploration of the methodology in historical linguistics, focusing on language subgrouping. Employing Tangut, a severely eroded mediaeval language, as a case study, it scrutinises previous linguistic analyses that depart from the rigorous Neogrammarian method, specifically referencing Beaudouin (2023). These non-compliant analyses have impeded recent progress in understanding the genetic relationships within Burmo-Qiangic, a field marked by prolonged debates and with gradual advancement recently. In a subsequent step, adhering to Neogrammarian principles, namely, *Ausnahmslosigkeit der Lautgesetze* and positive shared innovations in language subgrouping, the paper discusses the plausibility of, as well as the good practice to argue for a “Tangut-Horpa clade” within the Gyalrongic branch of Burmo-Qiangic. By advocating for the universality of these Neogrammarian principles, the paper aims to improve the accuracy and reliability of subgrouping languages characterised by significant typological diversity. This, in turn, contributes to a deeper comprehension of rigorous methodology within the context of the Sino-Tibetan language family.

Keywords: historical linguistics, language subgrouping, the Neogrammarian method, shared innovation, Tangut, Horpa (Gyalrongic), Sino-Tibetan

1. Introduction

Sino-Tibetan historical linguistics is still in its early stages of development. This is mainly due to a lack of data from conservative branches and a limited understanding of the internal morphology in eroded language varieties. As a result, a substantial portion of research in this domain does not fully embrace the Neogrammarian method, particularly in the context of subgrouping.

With the increasing emphasis on quantitative analysis in historical linguistics, computational methods, such as Bayesian inference in phylogeny, have gained significant traction (Gray and Atkinson 2003). For instance, Sagart et al. (2019) and Zhang Menghan et al. (2019) have produced phylogenetic trees for Sino-Tibetan languages using Bayesian inference. While quantitative methods often align with linguistic intuitions, they have received criticisms (see for example DeLancey 2021). Thus, the primary role of such quantitative methods is to assist historical linguists rather than replace traditional linguistic analysis, as emphasised by List et al. (2017: 2) and Greenhill et al. (2020: 230). Therefore, there is still an urgent need for detailed qualitative analysis, employing the rigorous Neogrammarian Method, to determine language subgrouping within Sino-Tibetan.

This paper focuses on the genetic position of Tangut, with a primary emphasis on the recent debates surrounding the genetic relationship between Tangut and modern Gyalrongic, as initiated by Jacques (2014) and Lai et al. (2020). This choice serves two crucial purposes in achieving the paper’s ultimate goal of illustrating a systematic, methodologically sound approach to language subgrouping in the Sino-Tibetan context. First, among the various Sino-Tibetan branches, modern Gyalrongic languages stand out as particularly conservative, providing valuable insights into the Sino-Tibetan family tree, as noted by Sun (2000a; b), Jacques (2014), and Lai and List (2023). Second, as a mediaeval Sino-Tibetan language that

* This research is supported by the Irish Research Council under the SFI-IRC Pathway Programme (Project ID: 21/PATH-A/9374, Gyalrongic unveiled: Languages, Heritage, Ancestry; Lai Yunfan) and the Horizon Europe Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions Postdoctoral Fellowship (101110215 Kinship Systems in Gyalrong: History and Transformation; Zhang Shuya). We would like to thank Nathan Hill, Sami Honkasalo, and Laurent Sagart for their constructive comments. We also extend our gratitude to the three anonymous reviewers for their valuable suggestions. All the remaining errors are ours.

became extinct around the 16th century, there are enduring debates concerning Tangut's genetic affiliation. The challenges associated with Tangut, such as its eroded phonology, obscure morphology, and the complexity of its script, have led to inconclusive results in past discussions regarding its linguistic classification.

The paper aims to address two key objectives. First, it seeks to provide a right track towards answering the question of Tangut's place within Sino-Tibetan based on the rigorous Neogrammarian method. Second, it utilises the subgrouping of Gyalrongic as a representative case study to demonstrate a way to identify shared innovations, encompassing both languages with conservative morphology as well as those with eroded morphology. This will serve as a valuable reference for the application of the Neogrammarian method in the subgrouping of Sino-Tibetan.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 introduces the general methodology of the Neogrammarian Method in language subgrouping, emphasising its universal validity with examples from Indo-European, Semitic and the Sino-Tibetan branches (Sinitic, Tibetic and Kiranti). Section 3 returns to the issue of the affiliation of Tangut within Sino-Tibetan. It is juxtaposed with our comments on a recent study conducted by Beaudouin (2023) that attempted to subgroup Tangut and Horpa (West Gyalrongic), which serves as an illustration of the incorrect application of the Neogrammarian Method. Section 4 proposes several directions to discuss the plausibility of the Tangut-Horpa clade based on the Neogrammarian Method, before coming to the conclusion in Section 5.

2. The universality of the Neogrammarian method in language subgrouping

In this section, we briefly comment on the general methodology in historical linguistics, with a focus on its principles of language subgrouping. In Section 2.1, we discuss the concepts of “cognate” and “cognacy”, along with the technique for identifying them. In Section 2.2, we emphasise the gold standard of language subgrouping in Neogrammarian historical linguistics, which is shared innovations.

2.1. The search for cognacy

Historical linguistics is built on genetic relations of words or parts of words (morphemes), i.e. cognacy and cognates (see Trask (2000: 62-63) and Campbell and Mixco (2007: 33-34), among others, for a definition of “cognacy” and “cognate”). The identification of cognates is a fundamental step towards language subgrouping. Ever since Osthoff and Brugmann (1878: XIII), who stated that “[...] alle wörter [...] werden ohne ausnahme von der änderung ergriffen (all words are subject to change without exception)”, the principle of *Ausnahmslosigkeit* has been the benchmark for identifying cognacy. In practical terms, the process of identifying cognates requires a meticulous approach.

The real world of languages frequently diverges from the ideal, with sound correspondences often deviating due to the unique evolutionary paths that each language has undergone. These complexities can obscure the recognition of cognates. For instance, Middle Chinese 署 *dzò* ‘to place, to position’ shows no superficial similarity with the related Gyalrongic forms such as Japhug *ta* ‘to place’, Bragbar Situ *tâ* ‘to place’, Siyewu Khroskyabs *s-tî* (< *[e-]tæ) ‘to place’ and Tangut 𑖇⁵⁴⁴⁹ *tji*^l ‘to place’ (< Pre-Tangut *S-tja^l). However, an internal reconstruction of the Old Chinese (abbreviated as “OCh.”) form, *m-taʔ-s, would reveal that they are actually related.¹ The stem of the Chinese form, *taʔ, is regularly related to the Gyalrongic forms. The rhyme correspondence pattern is also found in OCh. 斧 *p(r)aʔ :: Japhug *tu-rpa* :: Bragbar *ɛv-rpiê* (< *ɛv-rpâ) :: Siyewu *rvi* (< *rǎ.pæ):: Tangut 𑖇⁵²⁰³ *wi*^l (< *Sǎ.pa), all meaning ‘axe’ (Zhang Shuya et al. 2019; Lai 2022). While all the languages above share the same bare stem, they underwent different morphological processes which triggered distinct pathways of sound changes, resulting in the non-resemblance of the attested forms.² Without the internal reconstruction of Old Chinese, we would never discover that the original stem of 署 *dzò* ‘to place, to position’ has Gyalrongic cognates.

Instances of such blurred cognates commonly arise within language families marked by significant typological diversity. Therefore, the search for cognates in Sino-Tibetan needs careful examination, requiring

¹ We adopt the Old Chinese reconstruction of Baxter and Sagart (2014), and the Pre-Tangut reconstruction of Jacques (2014).

² In Old Chinese, The affixes *m- and *-s are added to the Chinese bare stem *taʔ. A possible speculation is that the suffix *-s was first added to *taʔ to form an event nominal *taʔ-s meaning ‘positioning’, before receiving the prefix *m- to become a volitional verb *m-taʔ-s meaning ‘place, position (v)’. See Downer (1959) and Zhang (2022) among others for Old Chinese event nominalisation and Baxter and Sagart (2014: 54-55) for volitional derivation.

a profound understanding of the internal and historical morphology of the languages in question.³ We will address this issue by providing detailed analyses focusing on the cognacy among Gyalrongic numerals in Section 3.3.

2.2. Shared innovations

While the presence of cognacy indicates that two languages share a common ancestor, cognacy alone is not enough to determine language subgrouping. Admittedly, regular correspondences from cognate sets like Sanskrit *bhārāmi*, Greek *pherō* and Latin *ferō*, all meaning ‘to.carry.1SG.IND’ indicate that these three languages are derived from a common source, but they do not tell us about their internal subgrouping. To obtain a plausible classification of related languages, one must search for shared innovations.

Although it was Schleicher (1853: 787) who drew the first *Stammbaum* for related languages, one had to wait until Leskien (1876: vii) to propose an explicit criterion to establish this tree:

“Die Kriterien einer engeren Gemeinschaft können nur in positiven Uebereinstimmungen der betreffenden Sprachen, die zugleich Abweichungen von den übrigen sind, gefunden werden (The criteria of a closer community can only be found in positive agreements of the respective languages in question, which are also deviations from the others).”

The “positiven Uebereinstimmungen (positive agreements)” mentioned above would soon be dubbed “positive shared innovations”, or more often just “shared innovations” in the English literature. Shared innovations remain the sole criterion for proving a subgroup among related languages.

When an ancestral language splits into two varieties, say A and B, the latter two must have evolved individually through time and become distinct from each other, by modifying phonological systems, replacing vocabulary, transforming morphology and so on. All these individual changes can be considered innovations that distinguish A from B. After the split, A and B would continue to evolve and become each the ancestor of their own descendants. The descendants would inherit a subset of the characteristics of A or B, amongst which some of said innovations would be present. Descendants that share A’s innovations would all be under the A clade, and those that share B’s innovation would all be considered members of the B clade. In practice, the vast majority of sister languages belonging to the same sub-branch exhibit shared innovations in one way or another. See Figure 1 for a graphic illustration.

Figure 1. Shared innovations as the sole criterion for language subgrouping

2.2.1. Defining shared innovation

While the principle of shared innovation is intuitive, it is crucial to exercise caution when establishing shared innovation to avoid misconceptions. This section explores concepts often confused with shared innovation, including homoplasy, shared retention, and negative innovation. Confusing shared innovation with these can lead to pitfalls in language subgrouping.

Shared innovations VS. homoplasy. Generally, homoplasy occurs when similarities observed in two languages are not attributed to a shared heritage, such as being purely coincidental or typological commonalities. A typical example of homoplasy concerns the auxiliary perfective in French and German.

³ A plausible method is formulated in Meelen et al. (2022), which provides a systematic workflow to disentangle these complexities and to classify cognate types. The workflow commences with a heuristic search for potential cognates, followed by the alignment of phonological segments to identify sound correspondences. After this step, it is essential to categorise the cognates under examination and ascertain their cognacy level. Finally, the process involves the extension and refinement of correspondence sets through additional comparisons.

Both languages exhibit perfective constructions with two auxiliaries depending on the verb: one translated as “to be”, Fr. *être*, Ger. *sein*, the other translated as ‘to have’, Fr. *avoir*, Ger. *haben*. The distribution of ‘to be’ and ‘to have’ presents some overlap between French and German cognates or homonymies, such as Ger. *kommen* / Fr. *venir* ‘to come’ (from Proto-Indo-European **gwem-*, auxiliary: ‘to be’), Ger. *holen* ‘to get’ / Fr. *clamer* ‘to call’ (from Proto-Indo-European **kel(ə)-* or **kal-*, auxiliary: ‘to have’).⁴ If we look closer at the auxiliary perfective in both languages, we may find ten or more such examples. However, such overlap is a superficial coincidence, and certainly does not validate French and German as a separate sub-branch, not to mention the many mismatches that contradict the subgrouping of French and German within Indo-European.

Shared innovation VS. shared retention. Retention can be misleading in language sub-grouping. If two languages exhibit a certain degree of genetic relationship, we anticipate that they have inherited features not only from their most recent common ancestor’s innovations, but also from what has always existed in higher nodes of the *Stammbaum*. However, we cannot, in turn, rely on shared retention to determine the closeness of languages. From a pure lexical perspective, Zhang Shuya et al. (2019) listed about 100 cognates shared between Gyalrongic and Chinese, which represent the oldest layer of Sino-Tibetan vocabulary. Nevertheless, these cognates cannot definitively establish a Chinese-Gyalrongic clade. The same goes for morphological evidence. Kiranti and Gyalrongic languages both retain the second person prefix in **tV-* (Jacques 2012; DeLancey 2014), however, this shared retention is obviously insufficient to support them forming a clade within Sino-Tibetan.⁵

Positive innovation VS. negative innovation. While shared innovation as the sole criterion for language subgrouping is easy to understand, people tend to forget the adjective “positiv (positive)” in Leskien’s passage. In the context of language subgrouping, one must exercise particular vigilance when confronted with the phenomenon of negative innovation. It is true that there are instances where the so-called shared negative innovations can be identified within the confines of a specific language branch. However, employing shared loss as a foundational premise for subgrouping is fraught with risks, since in many cases, a loss of a feature is highly random, meaning that sometimes a claimed “shared loss” among languages is merely a matter of coincidence. The Proto-East-Gyalrongic yod unspecified orientation prefix **jV-* has been lost in Zbu (Northern Gyalrong) and Bragbar (Situ Gyalrong) (Gong 2018; Zhang 2020). However, we cannot extrapolate from this that Zbu and Bragbar constitute a single clade. Similarly, the Proto-Gyalrongic rhotic unspecified orientation prefix **rə-* is preserved in Zbu, but was lost in Bragsteng (Situ Gyalrong), as well as in Japhug and Tshobdun (Northern Gyalrong) (Zhang 2023b). Again this “shared loss” by no means supports a Bragsteng-Japhug-Tshobdun clade. Moreover, relying on the shared loss of orientation prefixes would make the subgrouping of the mentioned Gyalrongic varieties an unsolvable puzzle.

2.2.2. The idiosyncratic nature of shared innovations

The application of shared innovation in language subgrouping demands further scrutiny. Some “innovations” may appear to be shared, but they could be homoplastic changes or common borrowings that offer limited insights into language subgrouping.

Hetzron (1976) proposed to look for “innovations which are as arbitrary as possible [...] and as little likely to be borrowed as possible”. He considered morpholexicon is the decisive type to look for. By “morpholexicon”, Hetzron (1976) meant morphological components serving as derivational and inflectional operators, such as affixes. He believed that inflectional affixes are the least subject to borrowing, and provided a successful demonstration of using shared morpholexical or morphological innovations to deal with the subgrouping of Semitic languages.

Hetzron (1976) compared a variety of morphological operations and affixes in Semitic, and found that Ethiopian, South-Arabian, Aramaic, Arabic and Canaanite innovatively turned the original permansive marker into a past marker. Such a positive shared innovation is sufficient for justifying a distinct branch, namely “West Semitic”, as opposed to Akkadian (East Semitic) retaining the most archaic forms. Furthermore, under West Semitic, two branches, South and Central Semitic, have been identified with morphological innovations. South Semitic (i.e. Ethiopian and South Arabian⁶) are marked by the

⁴ The Indo-European forms are from Pfeifer (1993).

⁵ Phylogenetic analysis revealed that Kiranti and Gyalrongic are probably distant relatives that branched off as different clades more than 5500 years ago (Sagart et al. 2019).

⁶ Here South Arabian in Hetzron (1976) does not refer to the old South Arabian languages, comprising four extinct languages, Sabaic, Qatabanic, Hadramitic, Minaic.

generalisation of *-k-* in the past tense and that of a closed vowel in verbal prefixes; while Central Semitic (i.e. Arabic, Canaanite and Aramaic) introduced the jussive *+u* and generalised *-t-* in the past tense. Finally, within Central Semitic, the feminine plural *-na* was innovatively adopted by Arabic and Canaanite, providing solid evidence for the latter two to form a sub-branch as opposed to Aramaic.

The concept of shared innovations being arbitrary is a well-accepted notion among historical linguists, described using various terms like “significant”, “non-trivial”, and “unusual” (Clackson 2022: 25). Notably, in the context of Sino-Tibetan, Sun (2023) employed “highly-idiosyncratic” shared lexical and phonological innovations to demonstrate that Gserskad and Rdoskad, formerly considered Amdo Tibetan dialects, actually constitute a distinct subgroup within Tibetic.

The Neogrammarian subgrouping methodology has yet to be extensively applied to Burmo-Qiangic (Sino-Tibetan). Prior to Jacques and Pellard (2021), a systematic investigation of shared lexical innovations to identify Burmo-Qiangic was lacking. Little attention has been paid to phonology and morphology. Using Tangut as a case in point, the remainder of this paper aims to illustrate how we can uncover the genetic relationship between Tangut within Gyalrongic (Burmo-Qiangic) through positive shared innovations, especially in phonology and morphology.

3. Tangut as an alleged Horpa language

The quest for Tangut’s affiliation serves as an illustrative example of the imperative need for adequate methods in language subgrouping in Sino-Tibetan.

Since the early 20th century, Tangut has been tentatively linked to what is now known as the Burmo-Qiangic languages, encompassing Qiang (or Rma) varieties, Lolo-Burmese, and Gyalrongic languages. These early associations primarily relied on lexical and grammatical similarities (Laufer 1916; Wolfenden 1931; Nishida 1976; Sun 1991). Matisoff (2004) attempted to use vowel “brightening” or vowel heightening (e.g., **a > i*) as an argument for associating Tangut with Qiangic, but this phenomenon seems to be more of an areal feature observed in individual Qiangic languages rather than a shared innovation (Chirkova and Handel 2019; Lai 2022; Hill 2022).

Jacques (2014) first revealed a close genetic relationship between Tangut and modern Gyalrongic languages by identifying shared lexical innovations. Subsequently, Lai et al. (2020) conducted a more comprehensive analysis of shared lexical, phonological, and morphosyntactic innovations between Tangut and West Gyalrongic (including Horpa and Khroskyabs), ultimately concluding that Tangut is specifically affiliated with West Gyalrongic. The classification implied in Lai et al. (2020) is shown in Figure 2. The qualitative analysis aligns globally with the Bayesian inference conducted by Sagart et al. (2019). While Lai et al. (2020) does not explicitly specify the relationship among Tangut, Horpa and Khroskyabs, the *Stammbaum* in Sagart et al. (2019) places Tangut as the first branch of West Gyalrongic, grouping Khroskyabs and Horpa in a separate clade, as reproduced in Figure 3. Thus, although it is quite clear that Tangut is closer related to modern West Gyalrongic, its precise position within this branch remains uncertain.

Figure 2. Gyalrongic subgrouping according to Lai et al. (2020)

Figure 3. Gyalrongic subgrouping according to Sagart et al. (2019)

Beaudouin (2023) claimed to be the first dedicated study to demonstrate a close affinity between Tangut and Horpa within West Gyalrongic. However, as will be shown in Section 4, the notion of Tangut-Horpa proximity can be traced back to the 1960s. While the Tangut-Horpa clade itself cannot be immediately dismissed, Beaudouin (2023) suffered from major methodological errors, specifically swapping the concept of shared innovation. These methodological errors have led to difficulties in the description of Tangut grammar and constitute a significant setback in the field of language subgrouping in Gyalrongic and Qiangic.

This section explores several dilemmas in Beaudouin's (2023) analysis⁷ due to methodological errors through Sections 3.1 through 3.3, and provides proper analyses for the illustrated data.⁸

3.1.1. False similarity between Tangut 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- and Geshiza *dæ*-

Tangut attests two series of verbal prefixes known as orientation prefixes or directional prefixes in the literature. The Series A prefixes exhibit a dual function, simultaneously fulfilling a primary perfective role and conveying certain spatial semantics.⁹ The prefix 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- has traditionally been as a Series A prefix, associated with the spatial semantics of translocative or 'loss' (Chang 2004; Kepping 1985).

Beaudouin (2023: 624, §2.2.4) departed from the traditional analysis, advocating that the orientation prefix 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- had lost its spatial meaning and serves only as a perfective (or, in his words, a "true change of state") in Tangut. Furthermore, he claimed that the Tangut 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- and the Geshiza orientation prefix *dæ*- exhibit distributional similarities, which he used as evidence to support the Tangut-Horpa clade. However, Beaudouin's proposed analysis suffers from methodological inappropriateness and factual inaccuracy.

On the one hand, Beaudouin failed to illustrate internal evidence supporting Tangut 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- as a "true change of state" with "semantic inadequacy of the orientational/modal interpretations", as he claimed in §2.2.4.1, Page 624. There is no textual example in the article to demonstrate the "true change of state" use of 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- in Tangut; textual examples were only given for other Series A prefixes that convey transparent or fictive orientation meanings (such as 𑖇¹⁴⁵² *nja*¹-, 𑖇²⁵⁹⁰ *wji*²-, 𑖇⁰⁷⁹⁵ *rji*²-, see Beaudouin 2023: 628-630, §2.2.4.2). The presence of orientation meanings with other Series A prefixes by no means supports the argument that 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²-, as member of the same paradigm, lost orientation meanings.

On the other hand, Beaudouin (2023: 630-632, §2.2.4.3) over-relied on external evidence from Geshiza to support his proposal of 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- as a generic perfective that lost its orientational meaning. He pointed out that Tangut 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- and Geshiza *dæ*- "have the same distribution on the whole" (Beaudouin 2023: 631, 2nd line). Nevertheless, this alleged "same distribution" is a false similarity.

⁷ The Gyalrongic languages cited in this paper include East Gyalrongic: Situ (Cogtse, Bragbar), Japhug, Zbu, and West Gyalrongic: Khroskyabs (Siyuewu, Wobzi, Guanyinqiao; Siyuewu is used as the default dialect), Horpa: Stau (Mazur, Khang.gsar, Bra'go, Stosde, Rtsang.khog, "Danba Ergong" as in Zàngmiányǔ Yǔyīn hé Cíhuì Biānxiězǔ 1992 and "Daofu" as in Huang and Dai 1992), Geshiza, Bawang, Phosul; Qiangic languages with unconfirmed relationship with Gyalrongic: Choyul, Munya. Precise citations will be provided in conjunction with the paper's content. In order to avoid ambiguities, we use the following conventions when citing content in Beaudouin (2023): Sections: §, tables: Tab., Figures: Fig., and Footnotes: Ft.

⁸ Beaudouin's paper exhibits some bibliographic deficiencies. Notably, he failed to acknowledge Honkasalo (2019) for the analyses of modal negators and the numeral 'five' (Beaudouin 2023: §2.2.7, §3.1); Jacques (2007; 2011; 2014) regarding the Tangut verbal template, modal negators and modal prefixes (Beaudouin 2023: §2.1, §2.2.7, §2.2.8); Zhang (2020) for the historical analysis of orientation prefix *rv-* in Bragbar and the historical evolution of Situ orientation systems (Beaudouin 2023: §2.2.2); Yin (2007) for Njorogs (Yelong) data. The sections on the case markers (Beaudouin 2023: §4.1) and the inferential marker (Beaudouin 2023: §2.3.3) present a patchy citation of Lai et al. (2020). Additionally, Beaudouin (2023) includes inaccurate descriptions of Tangut, such as the "determinative" analysis of the nominaliser 𑖇³⁹¹⁶ *-sji*² (Beaudouin 2023: §3.2.2), the "general perfective" analysis of the orientation prefix 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- (Beaudouin 2023: §2.2.4), and the "telic" analysis of the future suffix 𑖇¹¹⁰¹ *-jij*¹ (Beaudouin 2023: §2.3.2). The analyses proposed by Beaudouin (2023) that deviate from the previous literature should be treated with caution.

⁹ The two series of orientation prefixes in Tangut are often noted Series A and B, or DIR1 and DIR2 in the literature. Prefixes from Series A are considered default forms and are used for perfective and imperative. Series B is derived from Series A, involving a prominent irrealis/optative function (see Kepping 1985; Gong 1993 among others).

First, it is important to note that Geshiza *dæ-* has been generalised as a standard perfective prefix (Honkasalo 2019: 545), and can theoretically be prefixed to any verb. If Tangut 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- were indeed a general perfective marker, we would expect it to have been generalised to a large number of verbs through analogy. Comparing two morphological systems that have clearly been flattened by analogy is risky, as analogy can spontaneously and independently apply in different branches.

Second, the claim of a “shared” distribution between Tangut 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- and Geshiza *dæ-* is not faithful to the linguistic data. In Beaudouin (2023: 633, Tab. 8), only ten verbs out of 27 that share the *dV-* prefix between Tangut and Geshiza; among them, only four can Beaudouin assert as a “true change of state”, i.e. excluding the semantic value of “direction” or “loss”. Therefore, the portion of this purported “shared” distribution is well under 40%. Beaudouin (2023: 631) attributed the nine instances that Tangut did not employ 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²-, while Geshiza had *dæ-* to insufficiency of data, explaining that “a cognate not preceded by 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- [...] does not imply that the association is impossible. It is possible that we simply do not have enough texts to ascertain it for the time being.” While insufficiency of data can sometimes be considered an excuse, the current data listed in Beaudouin’s (2023: 633, Tab. 8) is equally sufficient to illustrate the different distribution of Tangut 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- and Geshiza *dæ-*, contrary to his own claim.

Beaudouin’s (2023: 624-634§2.2.4) analysis of the Tangut 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- is comparable to the mock analysis trying to relate the French and German auxiliary perfective as a shared innovation, already seen in Section 2.2. The distribution of the generalised perfective marker *dæ-* in Geshiza necessarily overlaps with that of the Tangut 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²-, as well as its cognates in other Horpa languages that have not developed into a general perfective (such as Mazur Stau *tə-*, see Gates 2021 and also Section 4.2.4). Such coincidental overlap is not valid as a key piece of evidence for language subgrouping. Besides, this methodological error is accompanied with the circular reasoning, as Beaudouin (2023) assumes that Tangut 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²- must follow the usage of Geshiza *dæ-*, which in turns forced him to seek unfalsifiable explanations for apparent discrepancies.

The complexity of spatial semantics in Tangut orientation prefixes have been a subject of enduring debates. However, before investigating external comparisons, it is crucial to establish a reliable internal analysis (Kepping 1982; 1985; Lin 1987; Arakawa 2012; Chang 2020). Concerning the Tangut prefix 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*²-, its spatial meaning has long been recognised, and it does not contradict its grammatical function of encoding the perfective (Chang 2004, Kepping 1984). The translocative or ‘loss’ semantics is evident with verbs like 𐰇²⁵¹¹ *rjir*² ‘to leave’ (Example 1), 𐰇¹¹⁰⁵ *khjow*¹ ‘to give’, 𐰇³⁰⁷² *sjj*² ‘to die’, but opaque in combination with verbs such as 𐰇⁵⁷¹² *dzjwa*¹ ‘to finish’ (Example 2), 𐰇⁵⁹²¹ *zar*² ‘to be ashamed’ (see Chang 2020 and Zhang to appear in 2024 for a detailed account, see also Section 4.2.4). Such dual semantic structure is also observed in other orientation prefixes of Tangut (Zhang accepted, among others), as well as in modern Qiangic and Gyalrongic languages (Shirai 2009, etc.).

- (1) 𐰇²⁰⁵². 𐰇¹¹⁴² 𐰇³³⁸⁸ 𐰇⁵⁶¹⁴ 𐰇⁴³⁴²-𐰇²⁵¹¹
*xiwā*¹. *ljj*² *ŋwu*² *lwu*¹ *dja*²-*rjir*²
 Fan.Li to.cry to.cry DIR1.PFV:TSL-to.leave

范蠡涕泣而去。(Shi et al. 1993: 61)

“Fan Li left, crying.” (*The Grove of Categories* 03.27A.6)

- (2) 𐰇⁵¹⁴⁸ 𐰇²⁹³¹ 𐰇⁴³⁴²-𐰇⁵⁷¹², 𐰇⁴⁸⁴¹-𐰇⁴²²⁵ 𐰇¹²⁷⁸
*dzji*² *sej*¹ *dja*²-*dzjwa*¹ *djjj*²-*sja*¹ *jt*²
 crime to.count DIR1.PFV-to.finish DIR2.OPT-to.kill to.say

數罪畢，請殺之。(Shi et al. 1993: 53)

“(Yan Ying said to Jinggong) ‘I finished accounting for his crimes, kill him please.’” (*The Grove of Categories* 03.20A.4)

3.1.2. Shared retention as argument for language subgrouping

Beaudouin’s (2023: 640-644) discussion on argument indexation erroneously used shared retention of the third person suffix *-w as a pivotal proof to support that Tangut has a closer relationship with Horpa than with Khroskyabs in West Gyalrongic. However, this shared retention between Tangut and Horpa, not only

failed to support a Tangut-Horpa clade within West Gyalrongic, but it also complicated the position of Zbu (East Gyalrongic), the subgrouping of which had been elucidated as early as in Sun (2000a).

Beaudouin (2023: 641) cited Gong (2017: 33-34) regarding the similar behaviour of verb stems in Tangut and Zbu (East Gyalrongic). In many transitive scenarios, the Zbu Stem I *ndzé?* (to.eat.I) and Stem III *ndzo?* (to.eat.III) align distributionally with their counter-parts in Tangut, Stem A 𐞗𐞐⁴⁵¹⁷ *dzji^l* (to.eat.A) and Stem B 𐞗𐞐⁴⁵⁴⁷ *dzjo^l* (to.eat.B), respectively (see Table 1 for an illustration). The presence of rounded vocalism with *-o* in both languages indicates an old suffix **-w* for the third person patient of transitive verbs, which is still overtly attested in Situ (East Gyalrongic) (Jacques2009, Prins2017, Zhang2019).¹⁰ Beaudouin (2023: 642, Tab. 12) reproduced Gong’s (2017: 33) table, but concluded “striking similarities between mixed contexts of Tangut and the stem 3 of a core Gyalrong language, Zbu” (Beaudouin 2023: 641). This “striking similarity” is indeed valuable as a morphosyntactic parallelism between Tangut and Zbu. However, this parallelism represents a shared retention inherited from Proto-Gyalrongic.

After pointing out this shared retention between Tangut and Zbu, Beaudouin (2023: 642-643) further compared the transitive paradigm in Tangut with Khroskyabs and Horpa. In the Horpa-lects that Beaudouin examined, the 1SG → 3 scenario is indexed by a rounded suffix *-w* or *-u*, which is believed to be a cognate with the rounded vocalism in Tangut Stem B, 𐞗𐞐⁴⁵⁴⁷ *dzjo^l*. There is no cognate morpheme in the transitive paradigm of Khroskyabs. Beaudouin (2023: 668) acknowledged a common retention of the third person patient suffix **-w*, as he concluded, “my analysis of verb agreement [...] shows common retentions abandoned in Wobzi Khroskyabs”. However, this conclusion not only contradicts the principle of shared innovation, but also creates a dilemma regarding the position of Zbu within Gyalrongic. If the shared retention of the third person patient suffix **-w* holds to support a Tangut-Horpa clade, then one should posit a Tangut-Horpa-Zbu clade, as Zbu also retained this morphology.¹¹

Table 1. Indexation in the stem-alternating verb ‘to eat’ in Zbu and Tangut (Gong 2017: 33), in comparison with Khroskyabs cognate (Lai 2020)

	Zbu	Tangut	Khroskyabs (PST) ¹²
1SG → 3SG	<i>ⁿdzɔ-ŋ?</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵⁴⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ²⁰⁹⁸ <i>dzjo^lŋa²</i>	<i>o-dzi-æŋ</i>
3 → 1SG	<i>və-ⁿdzé-ŋ?</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ²⁰⁹⁸ <i>dzji^lŋa²</i>	<i>o-dzi-æŋ</i>
1PL → 3	<i>ⁿdzé-jə</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁸⁸⁴ <i>dzji^lnji²</i>	<i>o-dzi-j</i>
3 → 1PL	<i>və-ⁿdzé-jə</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁸⁸⁴ <i>dzji^lnji²</i>	<i>a-dzi-j</i>
2SG → 3	<i>tə-ⁿdzɔ?</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵⁴⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁶⁰¹ <i>dzjo^lnja²</i>	<i>o-dzi-n</i>
3 → 2SG	<i>tə-və-ⁿdzé?</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁶⁰¹ <i>dzji^lnja²</i>	<i>a-dzi-n</i>
2PL → 3	<i>tə-ⁿdzé-ŋə</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁸⁸⁴ <i>dzji^lnji²</i>	<i>o-dzi-n</i>
3 → 2PL	<i>tə-və-ⁿdzé-ŋə</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ 𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁸⁸⁴ <i>dzji^lnji²</i>	<i>a-dzi-n</i>
3SG → 3’SG	<i>ⁿdzɔ?</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ <i>dzji^l</i>	<i>a-dzid</i>
3’SG → 3SG	<i>və-ⁿdzé?</i>	𐞗𐞐 ⁴⁵¹⁷ <i>dzji^l</i>	<i>a-dzid</i>

Currently, there is no evidence supporting innovations in person indexation shared between Tangut and Horpa. The available evidence instead points to an innovation within the West Gyalrongic group, shared by Tangut, Horpa, and Khroskyabs. Table 1 presents Gong’s (2017) original comparison between Tangut and Zbu, alongside Khroskyabs equivalents based on Lai (2020). Gong (2017) first observed that the pattern of stem alternation shared between Tangut and Zbu does not hold for non-local scenarios. Zbu continues to distinguish between *ndzé?* (eat.I, non-local inverse) and *ndzo?* (eat.III, non-local direct). However, Tangut unified all non-local scenarios with 𐞗𐞐⁴⁵¹⁷ *dzji^l* (eat.A) which is cognate with Zbu *ndzé?* (eat.I, used in non-

¹⁰ It can also be found in more remotely in Northern Qiang (Huang and Zhou 2007).

¹¹ Bra’go, a conservative variety coda-wise within Horpa, exhibits *-wu* as the 1SG → 3 marker (Tunzhi 2019: 283-290), which probably points to a velar origin of this marker. If this is the case, the relevant sound correspondence between Modern Horpa and Tangut must be thoroughly revised before establishing cognacy between the Horpa suffix and the *o*-vocalism in Tangut, which is beyond the scope of this paper (P.C. Sami Honkasalo, 5 March 2024).

¹² The coda *-d* in *dzid* ‘to.eat’, which is non-etymological and probably an innovation in Khroskyabs, drops in presence of a suffix.

local inverse), indicating that Tangut treats all non-local scenarios as inverse. This pattern aligns with all West Gyalrongic languages (Jacques et al. 2017; Lai 2015; 2020; Lai et al. 2020). As demonstrated in Table 1, Khroskyabs invariably employs the inverse series of the past marker, *a-*.

3.2. Negative innovation as subgrouping evidence

As discussed in Section 2.2.1, negative innovations are much less reliable than positive ones as evidence of subgrouping. This section critiques Beaudouin’s (2023) use of a negative innovation to bolster the Tangut-Horpa clade.

Within Beaudouin’s (2023) work, the sole instance of shared innovation highlighted is the alleged shared loss of two orientation prefixes between Tangut and Horpa, *nV-* and *IV-*, or “dir.4” and “dir.5” in Beaudouin’s terms. As Beaudouin (2023: 622) asserted, “One of the most interesting points in the distribution relates to directions 4 and 5 [...] The loss of dir.4 and dir.5 in both Tangut and Horpa languages could be analyzed as a shared innovation”. Nonetheless, as is previously exemplified with the Gyalrongic unspecified orientation prefixes in Section 2.2.1, the “shared loss” of orientation prefixes in Gyalrongic is probably a coincidence, offering no insight in subgrouping.

It should also be pointed out that using shared loss of orientation prefixes as the basis for subgrouping leads to many dilemmas. First, as previously demonstrated with the loss of unspecified orientation prefixes in Gyalrongic, such a shared loss makes the issue of Gyalrongic subgrouping unsolvable. Second, it also blurs the relationship between Gyalrongic languages and other closely related Qiangic languages such as Munya and Ersu. The latter two languages, though their subgrouping is not the focus of Beaudouin (2023), were frequently discussed as comparative data to support a Tangut-Horpa clade and a distant relationship between Tangut and Khroskyabs (West Gyalrongic). As indicated in Beaudouin (2023: 619, Tab. 2), Munya, a Qiangic language with an unconfirmed relationship with Horpa, also exhibits the loss of dir.4 and dir.5, which would imply a Tangut-Horpa-Munya clade on the *Stammbaum* following the author’s analysis.¹³ However, a Tangut-Horpa-Ersu clade was also implied in Beaudouin’s (2023: 630–632, §2.2.4.3) claim of shared similarity among Tangut 𑖇⁴³⁴² *dja*²-, Geshiza *dæ-* and Ersu *t^he-* with the exclusion of Munya (emphasised by Beaudouin 2023: 632, Ft.26).

In terms of data accuracy, Beaudouin’s (2023: 622) claim on a “shared loss” of *nV-* and *IV-* between Tangut and Horpa is incorrect. Not all Horpa languages share such a loss. Northern Horpa retains dir.5: two varieties of Puxi Stod.sde (Puxi Proper, Sun 2000b; Dayili, Qu and Jingsong 2007) provide evidence of the cognate prefix *ldə-* meaning ‘upstream’. Hence, it is not accurate to conclude that Horpa languages have completely lost the *IV-* prefix.

The paradigm of orientation prefixes indeed can leave clues for language subgrouping within Gyalrongic. However, these clues are by no means based on shared loss. In Section 4.2.3, we examine evidence of paradigmatic innovations shared among different subgroups of Gyalrongic.

3.3. Faulty innovations based on hasty identification of sound correspondences

In this section, we focus on issues related to establishing cognacy and sound correspondences in Beaudouin (2023).

The most challenging analysis found in Beaudouin’s (2023: 651–654, Tab. 17) is the comparative examination of numerals. His analysis not only fails to adhere to the principle of *Ausnahmslosigkeit*, but also leaves behind an array of adverse implications for our comprehension of Tangut’s historical morphology, creating a convoluted scenario within the internal classification of West Gyalrongic. As we shall see in the following paragraphs, the purported shared phonological innovations proposed by Beaudouin (2023: §3.1) compelled an affiliation between Tangut and only one variety of Geshiza, disregarding both other Geshiza dialects and Horpa languages.

Thus, it is necessary to clarify the right sound correspondences and innovations exhibited in numerals. In order to do so, we reproduce a part of Beaudouin (2023: 652, Tab. 17) in Table 2. The red letters are considered “innovations” and the blue ones “retentions” by Beaudouin (2023). We start by summarising Beaudouin’s problems, before proposing the corresponding plausible analyses.

¹³ Beaudouin’s (2023: 619) Table 2 contains data inaccuracies. In dir.0 column, Beaudouin compares the rhotic unspecified orientation prefix 𑖇⁰⁷⁹⁵ *rjir*²- to the prefixes *ro-* and *rə-* in Kyomkyo, illustrates the Kyomkyo data in an ambiguous way “*ro-* (*rə-*)”, suggesting that *ro-* and *rə-* are the same in Kyomkyo. However, in Kyomkyo, *ro-* and *rə-* are two different prefixes, designating towards the mountain and towards the river, respectively (Prins 2017).

Table 2. Partial reproduction of the Table in Beaudouin (2023: 652)

NUM	Tangut	Geshiza	Mazur Stau	Siyuewu	Wobzi	Japhug	Munya
1	𐞗 ⁰¹⁰⁰ <i>lew^l</i>	<i>rəu</i>	<i>ro</i>	<i>rəy</i>	<i>râγ</i>	<i>ci / try</i>	<i>to-</i>
2	𐞗 ⁴⁰²⁷ <i>njii^l</i>	<i>wne</i>	<i>yne</i>	<i>ynəy</i>	<i>jnə</i>	<i>bnuz</i>	<i>nə-</i>
3	𐞗 ⁵⁸⁶⁵ <i>so^l</i>	<i>ws^{hu}</i>	<i>ysu</i>	<i>xsəm</i>	<i>çsəm</i>	<i>χsum</i>	<i>so-</i>
4	𐞗 ²²⁰⁵ <i>ljii^l</i>	<i>wzæ</i>	<i>γzə</i>	<i>vdə</i>	<i>vdə</i>	<i>kuβde</i>	<i>rə-</i>
5	𐞗 ¹⁹⁹⁹ <i>ɲwə^l</i>	<i>ɲuæ</i>	<i>ngvɛ</i>	<i>mɲád</i>	<i>mɲá</i>	<i>kumɲu</i>	<i>ɲa-</i>
6	𐞗 ³²⁰⁰ <i>tʂ^hjiw^l</i>	<i>wte^həu</i>	<i>γte^ho</i>	<i>xtey</i>	<i>fteú</i>	<i>kutʂɣɣ</i>	<i>te^hi-</i>

The coda -w in Tangut. Beaudouin (2023: 620, Ft. 17) explicitly identifies that Tangut -w and Geshiza -u in their forms for ‘one’ (𐞗⁰¹⁰⁰ *lew^l* and *rəu* respectively) and for ‘six’ (𐞗³²⁰⁰ *tʂ^hjiw^l* and *wte^həu* respectively) are a shared innovation. This alleged innovation, according to Beaudouin, is not shared by Mazur (Horpa), which exhibits *ro* ‘one’. However, Tangut -w and Geshiza -u are in fact both retentions. Mazur Stau *ro* shares with Tangut and Geshiza the vocalisation of the coda *-ɣ, probably through a *-w stage: *-eɣ > *-ew > *-ow > -o. The same correspondence is found in Mazur *zo* ‘edible root’ :: Geshiza *zəu* ‘*Potentilla anserina*’ (Khroskyabs *zôγ* ‘*Potentilla anserina*’) and Mazur *teo* ‘waist’ :: Geshiza *dzəu* ‘waist’ (Khroskyabs *jôγ* ‘waist’). The Tangut and Geshiza semi-vowel codas are admittedly innovated from a consonant, but compared to the Mazur form, they are a retention of the original coda. The full monophthongisation in Mazur is an innovation.

Beaudouin’s analysis would suggest that Tangut forms a clade with Geshiza, excluding Mazur, a conclusion that raises significant doubts.

The preinitial wC- in Geshiza. Beaudouin (2023: 653) considered that the preinitial wC- in Geshiza *wzæ* ‘four’ (Khroskyabs *vdə* ‘four’) was a retention, while the same preinitial in *wne* ‘two’ and *ws^{hu}* ‘three’ (Khroskyabs *ynəy* ‘two’ and *xsəm* ‘three’) was an innovation. However, this claim can be rejected.

Comparative study suggests that the w- in Geshiza *wzæ* ‘four’ is innovated, whereas w- in ‘two’ and ‘three’ are retentions. It suffices to look at the correspondences of Geshiza wC- and vC- with other West Gyalrongic languages. See Table 3.

Table 3. West Gyalrongic velar and labial preinitials

	Geshiza	Mazur	Siyuewu (Khros.)	Wobzi (Khros.)
millstone	<i>wvi</i>		<i>ɣvi</i>	<i>jvi</i>
shoe	<i>wzi</i>	<i>ɣzi</i>	<i>ɣzi</i>	<i>jzi</i>
wind	<i>wlæ</i>		<i>ɣlə</i>	<i>jlə</i>
wound	<i>wmæ</i>	<i>ɣmɛ</i>	<i>ɣmi</i>	<i>jmi</i>
water	<i>wrə</i>	<i>ɣrə</i>	<i>ɣdə</i>	<i>jdə</i>
belly	<i>wrə-mæ</i>		<i>ɣdú</i>	<i>jdú</i>
see	<i>vdə</i>	<i>vdu</i>	<i>vdé</i>	<i>vdé</i>
mouse	<i>vteə</i>	<i>vcə</i>	<i>fcə</i>	<i>fcə</i>
be satiated	<i>vk^hə</i>		<i>vɣi</i>	<i>vɣi</i>
mate	<i>vdzæ</i>	<i>vdzə</i>	<i>vdzə</i>	<i>vdzə</i>

As shown in Table 3, Geshiza wC- regularly corresponds to Mazur vC-, Siyuewu Khroskyabs vC- and Wobzi Khroskyabs jC-, which implies that the preinitial wC- in Geshiza *wne* ‘two’ and *ws^{hu}* ‘three’ are also regular and non-innovative, contrary to Beaudouin’s claim. On the other hand, Geshiza vC- regularly corresponds to vC- in all the other three languages (the fC- in Khroskyabs dialects are conditioned variants of vC-). Apart from Geshiza *wzæ* ‘four’ and a potential stative causative prefix w- which is attested with only one verb (*wzælə* ‘to peel’) (Honkasalo 2019: 428), there is no instance where Geshiza wC- corresponds to Khroskyabs vC- or to Japhug βC-. This observation implies that Geshiza *wzæ* ‘four’ and Mazur *γzə* ‘four’ have innovated their preinitials from a proto *v- to *ɣ- by contamination.

Beaudouin’s analyses complicated the understanding of sound correspondences among numerals in Gyalrongic. Such analyses failed to yield any conclusive findings regarding subgrouping, but more importantly, overlooked a genuine shared innovation in Horpa.

The preinitial in ‘six’. Concerning the numeral ‘six’, Beaudouin (2023: 653) seemed to have favoured the hypothesis that Mazur *ɣte^{ho}* and Siyuewu *xteéy* both innovated the velar preinitial *ɣ-/x-*, while confusingly colouring it in blue which indicates a retention.¹⁴

In reality, the velar preinitials in Siyuewu, Mazur and Geshiza in the numeral ‘six’ are all retentions, corresponding to *ku-* in Japhug *kutɕɣy* ‘six’. The labial preinitial in Wobzi *fteú* is a variant of *x-* influenced by the rounded vowel *-u*, thus **xteú > fteú* (Lai to appear in 2025).

The inaccurate recognition of shared innovations, stemming from inadequate engagement with West Gyalrongic morphology, did not lead to the internal classification of West Gyalrongic. Instead, it created confusion in our understanding of this branch.

The metathesis in ‘five’. The metathetical sound change **wŋ- > ŋw-* in the numeral ‘five’, shown in Tangut 𐞗¹⁹⁹⁹ *ŋwə^l*, Geshiza *ŋuə* and Mazur *ngve* is the only plausible analysis concerning numerals in Beaudouin (2023: 652). This sound change was first proposed by Honkasalo (2019: 314), which was not properly acknowledged in Beaudouin’s work.

In any case, the metathesis **wŋ- > ŋw-* is not a shared innovation between Tangut and Horpa. First, this particular metathesis is rather areally trivial, commonly found in Burmo-Qiangic, as exemplified by Ersu *ŋwá-* (Chirkova 2014), also cited in Beaudouin (2023: 652), Jiulong Prinmi *ŋuə* and Xinlong Choyul *ŋua⁵⁵* (Huang and Dai 1992), all meaning ‘five’. It is difficult to exclude the possibility that the sound change in question is an individual innovation. Second, Honkasalo (2019: 314) cites the Geshiza form *wŋə* ‘five’ noted by Duo’erji (1998: 88), which probably comes from a more conservative Geshiza variety. Should the metathesis in question be a shared innovation, one would have to admit that Honkasalo’s Geshiza is closer to Tangut than to Duo’erji’s Geshiza, despite the fact that the two Geshiza varieties are mutually intelligible.

4. Evaluating the Tangut-Horpa clade based on shared innovations

The idea about a close relationship between Tangut and Horpa has been circulating for over half a century. It was first proposed by Stein (1966: 285), who speculated that “il est désormais certain qu’on trouvera des parents beaucoup proches du si-hia parmi les langues diverses parlées dans les régions de Hor Kandze, Tao-fou (Ta’o), Mi-ñag (Tatsienlou), Kin-tch’ouan (It is now certain that we will find relatives very close to Tangut among the various languages spoken in the regions of Hor Kandze (Hor Dkar.mdzes, 霍爾甘孜 Huò’ěr Gānzī), Tao-fou (Ta’o) (Rta’u, 道孚 Dào fú), Mi-ñag (Tatsienlou) (Dar.rtse.mdo, 康定 Kāngding), Kin-tch’ouan (Chu.chen, 金川 Jīnchūān)).”¹⁵ Later, based on a preliminary comparison of core vocabulary, Li and Lin (1983) deemed that Tangut is most closely related to Horpa-lects, and further proposed that Horpa speakers were descendants of the Tangut people. In the past decade, informal consensus has emerged that Tangut was closer to Horpa than to Khroskyabs among Gyalrongic specialists.¹⁶ The evidence in support for a Tangut-Horpa clade has been sporadically mentioned among different authors, which now only requires a systematic presentation.

Contemporary works that implicitly suggest a closer relation between Tangut and Horpa begin with Gong (2017: 33-34), who noted that Tangut shares with Dgebshe Horpa the neutralisation of inverse to non-local scenarios (although this phenomenon turned out to be an innovation of the entire West Gyalrongic branch, see Table 1). Lai et al. (2020) also highlights more shared innovations in terms of case marking and modal markers between Tangut and Horpa than between Tangut and Khroskyabs. Honkasalo (2019: 646) identifies a similar distribution of “basic” and “modal” negative prefixes in Tangut and Geshiza (also mentioned in Gates et al. 2022: 236). Zhang (2020; 2023b; accepted) uncovered non-trivial shared innovations of orientation prefixes between Tangut and Horpa. Additionally, Lai (2023: 27) asserts a Tangut-Horpa clade within West Gyalrongic, presented in the form of a partial *Stammbaum*, based on the evolution of a set of voiceless nasals in Proto-Gyalrongic.

¹⁴ The original text reads: “For that numeral (‘six’), two scenarios seem possible. Geshiza and Wobzi forms could be innovative, as could be Stau and Siyuewu forms. I favor the second hypothesis [...]” (Beaudouin 2023: 653).

¹⁵ These places mentioned cover the majority of Horpa-speaking area.

¹⁶ For example, Jesse Gates, Yunfan Lai, and Guillaume Jacques exchanged emails discussing the hypothetical *mo* in Mazur Stau as a shared innovation with 𐞗⁰⁷³⁴ *mo²* ‘IRR’, excluding Khroskyabs, from 6 to 14 September 2017; and when asked about the relationship of Tangut with regards to Khroskyabs and Horpa in an email correspondence on 21 February 2019, Guillaume Jacques wrote, “je pencherais pour la deuxième” (I would go for the second).

The purpose of this section is not to claim the final word on the Tangut-Horpa clade within Gyalrongic. Our goal is to propose a plausible framework for demonstrating this subgrouping, emphasising the data and aspects that should be considered when encountering similar languages and circumstances. Here, we present evidence currently available in the literature that supports said clade, offering comments, additional data, and conditions for refutation. Section 4.1 focuses on phonological evidence, including the reflexes of proto voiceless nasals (Section 4.1.1) and the behaviour of preinitials (Section 4.1.2), Section 4.2 on shared morphological innovations, encompassing the negator for modal verbs (Section 4.2.1), case markers (Section 4.2.2), pairing of orientation prefixes (Section 4.2.3), as well as their lexicalisation (Section 4.2.4).

4.1. Phonological evidence

There has yet to be a detailed and comprehensive phonological account of the relation between Tangut and Horpa. Recently, there are two papers to discuss specific topics in the comparative phonology of West Gyalrongic, which both point to a closer relationship between Tangut and Horpa. Lai (2023) analysed the evolution of Proto-Gyalrongic voiceless nasals; and Lai (to appear) used Mutual Implicative Entropy to study preinitial correspondences among Gyalrongic languages.

4.1.1. Development of voiceless nasals

Lai (2023) reconstructed a series of voiceless nasal initials in Proto-Gyalrongic, namely * η -, * η -, * η -, * η - and * η -, which have non-trivial reflexes including nasals and different kinds of stops in daughter languages, depending on the position of the voiceless nasal. These reconstructed voiceless nasals are used to account for a small group of superficially irregular correspondences between nasals and stops, like Khroskyabs *snóy* vs Japhug *stob* ‘bean’ (* η -) and Geshiza *sq^har* vs Bragbar *tə- η iér* ‘phlegm’ (* η -).

Lai (2023) used data from Situ (Cogtse, Bragbar and Leilecun), Japhug and Zbu for East Gyalrongic, and Khroskyabs, Geshiza and Tangut for West Gyalrongic. These data show a general tendency that the reflexes of voiceless nasals in Tangut are more consistent with Geshiza than with Khroskyabs, implying a closer relationship between Tangut and Geshiza. This can be best illustrated by the reflexes for etymon ‘leaf’, reconstructed as * η p- η [æ]k. In both Tangut and Geshiza, the voiceless nasal * η - is reflected as *b*-: Tangut 𑖇𑖆^{4567} *bq²* and Geshiza *lbala* respectively, while in Khroskyabs, it derives *p^h-*: *lp^héc*. As shown in Table 4, the reflexes of * η - in * η p- η [æ]k ‘leaf’ is highly varied among Gyalrongic languages, with five different outcomes (*w*-, *b*-, *m*-, *v*- and *p^h-*). Despite the superficial randomness, Geshiza and Tangut both developed a voiced initial, rather than an aspirated initial as in Khroskyabs. This observation leads to the hypothesis that Tangut and Geshiza forms a separate sub-branch in West Gyalrongic.

Table 4. Reflexes of * η p- η [æ]k ‘leaf’ in Gyalrongic (extended from Lai 2023:25).

Cogtse	Bragbar	Leilecun	Japhug	Zbu	Tshobdun	Khroskyabs	Geshiza	Tangut
<i>tə-jwək</i>	<i>ta-jbák</i>	<i>tə-jmak</i>	<i>tx-jwək</i>	<i>tə-lvák</i>	<i>tə-lva?</i>	<i>lp^héc</i>	<i>lbala</i>	𑖇𑖆^{4567} <i>bq²</i>

While there is only one Horpa variety (Geshiza) in Lai (2023), a search into other varieties shows that other Horpa varieties invariably exhibit *b*- as the reflex of * η -, meaning that the analysis still stands. See Table 5.¹⁷

Table 5. Reflexes of * η p- η [æ]k ‘leaf’ in various Horpa-lects

Mazur	Bawang	Ergong (Danba)	Daofu
<i>rbala</i>	<i>jbala</i>	<i>lbala</i>	<i>lbalə</i>

The exact reconstruction of voiceless nasals in Proto-Gyalrongic is still open to future revision, however, the consistent innovative behaviour between Tangut and Horpa within the set of cognates in question is an indication for their subgrouping.

4.1.2. Towards a quantitative account of shared phonological innovations

¹⁷ Sources of data used: Mazur Stau (Gates 2021), Bawang Horpa (Yang 2021), Ergong (Danba) (Zāngmiānyǔ Yǔyīn hé Cíhui Biānxiězǔ 1992), Daofu (Huang and Dai 1992). “Ergong (Danba)” is very close to Bawang and Geshiza. “Daofu” is the Pinyin spelling of 道孚 *dào fú*, the Chinese phonetic interpretation of “Stau”.

Lai (to appear) introduces a new information-theoretical method to measure the degree of regularity of sound correspondences, namely the Mutual Implicative Entropy (MIE) method. This method involves four steps.

Firstly, a set of cognates (or suspected cognates) among sister languages is established. Secondly, the linguist observes the sound correspondences in the cognates and selects a specific group of phonemes deemed to contain the clearest phylogenetic signals. Depending on the language branch, this group of phonemes can include initial consonants, syllable nuclei, tones, and so on. The selected sound correspondences are then stored in a spreadsheet. Proceeding to the third step, the MIE between the selected sound correspondences of every pair of languages is computed to measure the predictiveness of sounds from one language to another, hence the regularity of sound correspondences. A high MIE value indicates low predictiveness, meaning that the sound correspondences of the two languages tend to be irregular. Conversely, a low MIE value indicates high predictiveness, meaning that it is easy to guess a sound from one language to the other. Thus, it is assumed that a high MIE value corresponds to a remote relationship between two languages, while a low MIE value corresponds to a close relationship. In the final step, a distance matrix featuring all language pairs and their corresponding MIE values is established, and a NeighborNet network is generated to visualise the inferred subgrouping of the family.

In order to apply the method to Gyalrongic languages, Lai (to appear) selects the correspondences of preinitials. Modern Gyalrongic languages exhibit various types of preinitials that may or may not correspond to each other, due to different pathways of splits and mergers. Although Tangut does not have segmental preinitials according to the common opinion, it contains traces of old preinitials that transphonologised into tense vowels, rhotic vowels, long vowels and rhymes with medials (Gong 1999; Jacques 2014; Gong 2021; Lai to appear). For instance, the proto-preinitial *k.C- typically results in γ C- in Khroskyabs, w C- in Geshiza, and undergoes transphonologisation into a tense vowel in Tangut (See Lai to appear for a detailed reconstruction of Tangut transphonologisation types). This is illustrated in the case of ‘shoe’ in Figure 4. However, in certain instances, both Tangut and Horpa introduce an innovative substitution for the original preinitial, namely *p.C-. This substitution yields v C- in Geshiza and a medial -w- in Tangut (Jacques 2014: 23, 29-30), illustrated in the case of ‘bird’ in Figure 4. The behaviour of *k.C- shows that Tangut and Geshiza share the same innovative phonological split, while Khroskyabs retains the original form. When such splits and mergers become too numerous to handle manually, the MIE method systematically takes them into account, forming the basis for statistically plausible subgrouping.

Figure 4. Shared split of *k.C- between Tangut and Horpa (Horpa variety used: Geshiza)

Figure 5 shows the NeighborNet inferred from the MIEs based on all the preinitials in Lai (to appear), which shows a clear division of East and West Gyalrongic, and Horpa dialects such as Geshiza and Bawang are visually closer to Tangut. In the network, the Tangut-Horpa clade has a weight of 0.1437, slightly higher than the Horpa-Khroskyabs clade, with a weight of 0.1225, marginally confirming the plausibility of a Tangut-Horpa clade.

Figure 5. Gyalrongic NeighborNet inferred from MIE

4.2. Morphological innovations

A careful examination reveals that most morphological similarities between Tangut and Horpa are shared retentions, rather than innovations. Moreover, some shared innovations identified by previous studies have proven to be problematic with new emerging data. For example, Lai et al. (2020: 193) and Gates (2021: 333-334) suggested that the vowel rising of the optative series of orientation prefixes from *-a- (as preserved in Khroskyabs and East Gyalrongic, see Lin 2003, Jacques 2008: 283, etc.) to -ij- (Tangut), -e- (Mazur) and -i- (Khang.gsar) represents a shared innovation between Tangut and Horpa. However, the *a*-vocalism presented in the Geshiza optative orientation series (Honkasalo 2019) questions this hypothesis of vowel rising as a shared innovation between Tangut and Horpa. This observation hints at the scarcity of confirmed morphological innovations shared between Tangut and Horpa, which require solid understanding of their morphology.

This section aims to provide indications of shared morphological innovations between Tangut and Horpa, which are potentially valid to the best of our knowledge. We will focus on negative prefixes (Section 4.2.1), locative and modal markers (Section 4.2.2), paradigms of orientation prefixes (Section 4.2.3) and lexicalisation of orientation prefixes (Section 4.2.4).

4.2.1. Innovated negator for modal verbs

Honkasalo (2019: 646) documented a special type of negative prefix *mə-* in Geshiza, as opposed to the neutral negator *mi-*, which only occurred before the eight modal verbs in that language. See (3) where the neutral negative prefix *mi-* marks the non-modal verb *kʰroyŋ* (catch.NPST.1PL), while the modal negative prefix marks the modal verb *mŋoyŋ* (MOD.NEG-AUX.can.1).

- (3) ə bæ ŋæ=jə ɟə mi-kʰroyŋ=gæ ə bæ ŋæ=jə ɟə
 HES Tibetan 1=PL fish NEG-to.catch.NPST.1PL HES Tibetan 1=PL fish
 kʰrə mə-mŋoyŋ
 to.catch.INF MOD.NEG-AUX.can.1
 ‘We Tibetans do not fish. We do not know how to fish.’ (Honkasalo 2019: 646-647)

Jacques (2011; 2014: 239-243) provided a detailed account for the allomorphy of negation in Tangut. Among the four negatives prefixes in Tangut, 𐞗𐞗⁵⁶⁴³ *mji*^l has the same modal distribution, while presenting perfect phonological correspondences with the Geshiza negative prefixes.

- (4) 𠵹⁰⁷⁹⁵-𠵹⁴⁴⁴⁴-𠵹⁵¹¹³ 𠵹⁵⁶⁴³-𠵹⁴⁴⁴⁴-𠵹⁵¹⁷⁶ 𠵹⁵⁹⁸¹-𠵹⁴⁴⁴⁴-𠵹⁴⁸⁵⁹
rji²-lji¹-wji¹ *mji¹-lji¹-dzioow²* *a²-lji¹-to²*
 DIR-CONCV-to.do NEG.MOD-CONCSV-may DIR1-CONCSV-to.end
 𠵹⁵⁶⁴³-𠵹⁴⁴⁴⁴-𠵹⁰¹³⁹
mji¹-lji²-nej²
 NEG-CONCSV-to.be.profitable
 ‘Although it is done, it is not satisfying; although it is completed, it is not profitable.’ (Tangut Proverbs 29a.3, Kychanov 1974: 122,209, cited from Jacques 2011: 431)

Honkasalo (2019: 646) cited Jacques’ (2011) observation about Tangut, clearly stating that “the negator *mə-* also exists in Stau with largely the same verbs as in Geshiza, but core Gyalrong languages lack the phenomenon. Presence of modal non-controllable negation can thus be seen yet another feature shared by Tangut and East [*recte* West] Gyalrong languages, illustrating the close affinity of the former in the latter”.

Although the same phenomenon is discussed in Beaudouin (2023: 636-637, §2.2.7) with slightly more data and Tangut texts, the recognition of this shared innovation should be attributed to Honkasalo (2019) concerning the shared innovation of negation morphology, which was however, not mentioned in Beaudouin’s passage.

4.2.2. Case/modal markers

Table 6 compares the case and modal markers in Khroskyabs, Horpa and Tangut. The comparison is based on Gates (2021: 311, 339-342, 346-347), Lai et al. (2020: 183, 193-196) and Zhang (2023a: 671). The glosses of the listed case markers in Tangut basically follows Arakawa (2010), with slight modifications according to more recent literature.¹⁸

Table 6. Case and modal markers in Horpa,¹⁹ Khroskyabs and Tangut

Khroskyabs		Horpa				Tangut
Wobzi	Siyuewu	Khang.gsar	Mazur	Stod.sde	Rtsang.khog	
= <i>yə</i> ERG	= <i>yə</i> ERG	- <i>w</i> ERG	= <i>yə</i> ERG			𠵹 ⁵⁸⁸⁰ <i>ɲwu²</i> INS
= <i>ji</i> GEN-ALL	= <i>jə</i> GEN-ALL	- <i>j</i> GEN	= <i>ji</i> GEN			𠵹 ¹¹³⁹ <i>jij¹</i> GEN-ACC-OBL
				= <i>do</i> DAT	= <i>do</i> DAT	𠵹 ⁵⁴⁴⁷ <i>do²</i> LOC
= <i>ka</i> LOC	= <i>ka</i> LOC	- <i>ka</i> ALL	= <i>ka</i> ALL			𠵹 ⁵⁸⁵⁶ <i>ya²</i> LOC
		- <i>te^ha</i> LOC	= <i>te^hæ</i> LOC			𠵹 ⁰⁰⁸⁹ <i>te^hjaa¹</i> LOC:above
		- <i>k^ha</i> INS	= <i>k^hæ</i> INS			𠵹 ⁵⁹⁹³ <i>k^ha¹</i> LOC:middle
= <i>si</i> IFR	= <i>si</i> IFR	- <i>sə</i> IFR	- <i>sə</i> IFR			𠵹 ³⁹¹⁶ <i>si²</i> IFR
			= <i>mo</i> IRR			𠵹 ⁰⁷³⁴ <i>mo²</i> IRR

Table 4.2.2 clearly demonstrates that Horpa and Tangut share four markers that are absent in Khroskyabs. Among these, three are discussed in detail in Gates (2021: 311, 339-342, 346-347) and Lai et al. (2020: 183, 193-196): (i) the locative marker *-te^ha* in Khang.gsar, =*te^hæ* in Mazur, and 𠵹⁰⁰⁸⁹ *te^hjaa¹* in Tangut; (ii) the

¹⁸ Arakawa (2010: 158) and Nishida (1989 [2012]: 479) suggested that 𠵹⁵⁸⁵⁶ *ya²* serves as an locative-accusative-dative (場所格-對格-與格). However, our analysis, based on *The Grove of Categories* (ed. Shi et al. 1993), *Newly Collected Biographies of Affection and Filial Piety* (ed. Jacques 2007), and *The Ode of Monthly Pleasure* (ed. Nishida 1986), does not find significant accusative or dative uses for 𠵹⁵⁸⁵⁶ *ya²*. Therefore we do not include accusative and dative in the gloss of 𠵹⁵⁸⁵⁶ *ya²* in Table 6. Additionally, we made a slight adjustment to Arakawa’s (2010) “genitive-accusative-dative” analysis for 𠵹¹¹³⁹ *jij¹*, and gloss 𠵹¹¹³⁹ *jij¹* as “genitive-accusative-oblique”, following Zhang (2023a) and emphasising its syntactic functions. The syntactic category of “oblique” encompasses the semantic recipients and bene/maleficiaries of multitransitive verbs. Jacques (2014: 210-211) previously labelled 𠵹¹¹³⁹ *jij¹* as “genitive/antiergative”, with “antiergative” following LaPolla (1992). The functions of 𠵹¹¹³⁹ *jij¹* are comparable to the Greek genitive. This similarity might imply that it could simply be described as “genitive”. However, we have chosen to underscore its unique functions, particularly in contrast to Horpa languages.

¹⁹ Stod.sde and Rtsang.khog data from Sun (2007) and Lai (2021).

instrumental marker $-k^h a$ in Khang.gsar, $=k^h a$ in Mazur, and 糝⁵⁹⁹³ $k^h a^l$ in Tangut; (iii) the irrealis marker Khang.gsar $=mo$ / 𐰇⁰⁷³⁴ mo^2 .

The comparison of (iv) the locative 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 in Tangut and the dative $=do$ in Rtsang.khog and Stod.sde is proposed by Zhang (2023a: 671).²⁰ The functional discrepancies between Tangut 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 and Horpa $-do$ is due to the fact that they represent different stages of grammaticalisation. The dental dative $-do$ in Horpa serves as an abstract case. For instance, in Rtsang.khog, it marks the subject of an indirect intransitive verb (Example 5), or in Stod.sde, it marks the causee (i.e. semantic recipient, Example 6). Their cognates in Tangut 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 primarily serves as a locative, allowing contextual interpretations of both static location (Example 7) or the goal of motion. In Tangut, 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 also encodes a semantic recipient (Example 8), as an extended use of locative, based on the interpretation of ‘at the place of’, ‘at the vicinity of’.

- (5) Rtsang.khog Horpa
 𐰇𐰏¹-do kormú nə-rô-n
 2SG-DAT money PST-to.have_{II}-2SG
 ‘You used to have money.’ (Lai 2021: 77)
- (6) Stod.sde Horpa
 𐰇𐰏¹mu-yə 𐰇𐰏¹ce-do sman dzo-ldo yə-vzo
 Lhamo-ERG child-DAT medicine to.eat-COMP DIR.PFV-to.make_{II}
 ‘Lhamu made the child take the medicine.’ (Sun 2007)
- (7) Tangut
 𐰇⁵⁹¹⁸ 𐰇¹⁹⁰⁶ 𐰇⁰²⁶¹ 𐰇²⁸⁶²=𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ 𐰇²⁵⁴¹=𐰇¹¹³⁹ 𐰇⁰⁷⁹⁵-𐰇¹²⁷⁸-𐰇⁴⁸⁸⁴
 sj^l nioow^l mjo² nji^l=do² dzjwo²=jij^l rjir²-ji²-nji²
 to.die_[I] LNK 1SG home=LOC people=OBL DIR.I.IMP-to.say-2PL
 死後告我家人曰... (Shi et al. 1993: 54)
 ‘After I die, tell my family (...)’ (*The Grove of Categories* 03.21B.3)
- (8) Tangut
 𐰇⁰⁵¹⁰ 𐰇⁵⁵⁴⁹ 𐰇⁴⁴⁵⁷ 𐰇⁰⁹⁴⁵ 𐰇⁵³⁰⁶=𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ 𐰇¹³²⁶-𐰇²⁸³⁰
 𐰇wə^l.te^hjiw² 𐰇lji² ts^hja^l dzjwi^l=do² kji^l-dju^l
 princess big to.be.angry emperor=LOC DIR.I.PFV-to.tell
 公主大怒，告帝。(Shi et al. 1993: 42)
 ‘The princess got very angry and told the emperor (about this matter).’ (*The Grove of Categories* 03.08A.7)

Proto-Gyalrongic likely did not possess a complex case system. The only case reconstructable for Proto-Gyalrongic is the yod locative $*=i$ (Jacques 2014: 210), which underwent a shared innovation in West Gyalrongic as a genitive (Zhang 2023a). Consequently, the aforementioned four markers shared between Horpa and Tangut, but absent in Khroskyabs as well as East Gyalrongic, are more likely to be shared innovations than retentions, thereby supporting a Tangut-Horpa clade.

4.2.3. Innovative pairing of orientation prefixes

As slightly mentioned in Section 3, Gyalrongic languages, together with its geographic neighbours, exhibit a series of orientation prefixes, or preverbs (see early discussions in Kepping 1984, Nishida 1986, Sun 2001, etc.) The orientation prefixes are considered to have a dual function, encoding spatial information and marking the TAME of the host verb. These prefixes are an essential part of the verbal morphology, and their

²⁰ Beaudouin (2021) proposed that Tangut 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 serves as both “terminative” and “dative”, and is cognate with the Geshiza terminative $lɔ$. We do not consider “terminative” as the primary source function of 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 , nor do we adopt the comparison with the Geshiza terminative $lɔ$. The “dative” analysis is not wrong from a semantic perspective, however, it is important to note that Tangut lacks a strictly dedicated dative case from a syntactic perspective. The two case markers, 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 and 𐰇¹¹³⁹ jij^l , are alternatively used to cover the functional domain commonly associated with a dative, including the semantic recipient and the beneficiary/malefactor of ditransitive verbs. For details on the distribution of 𐰇⁵⁴⁴⁷ do^2 and 𐰇¹¹³⁹ jij^l in ditransitive constructions, see Zhang (2023a: 653-659).

descriptions can be found in nearly every account of languages in this area. A most recent comparison of orientation prefixes from a Burmo-Qiangic scope is Shirai (2020).

Building upon Sun (2000a), Zhang (2023b; accepted) proposed a multi-axial model to account for the paradigms of orientation prefixes in Gyalrongic languages. Orientation prefixes are divided into groups. In most cases, each group is composed of two prefixes, denoting opposite directions of a spatial axis. There are also groups or axes that have only one member, typically expressing an unspecified orientation. The axes noted with Roman numerals represent the division of semantic categories of the orientation system in these languages, minimising interference from semantic divergence attested with orientation prefixes in modern Gyalrongic (see Zhang 2020: 495, Yang 2021: 133 for an illustration). Such a model has analytical benefits, as it helps us to examine shared paradigmatic innovations that could happen in terms of the pairing of orientation prefixes cross-Gyalrongic.

Table 7 is based on Zhang’s (2020: 488-490; 2023b: 210; accepted) comparison of the default Series A prefixes, with additional Horpa data from Gates (2021) and Yang (2021: 133).²¹

Table 7. Multi-axial analysis of orientation prefixes in Gyalrongic. Abbreviations: U: upward, D: downward, US: upstream, DS: downstream, E: East, W: West, CSL: cislocative, TSL: translocative, CF: centrifugal, CP: centripetal, IN: inward, OUT: outward, UNSP: unspecified.

Axis	Bragbar	Japhug	Khros.	G.yurong	Mazur	Bawang	Geshiza	Phosul	Tangut
I	<i>rv-</i> U	<i>ɬɻ-</i> U	<i>o-</i> U	<i>ə-</i> U	<i>rə-</i> U	<i>rə-</i> U	<i>rə-</i> U	<i>rə-</i> U	𐌷 ⁵⁹⁸¹ <i>a</i> ² U
	<i>na-</i> D	<i>puu-</i> D	<i>næ-</i> D	<i>nə-</i> D	<i>nə-</i> D	<i>nɐ-</i> D	<i>næ-</i> D	<i>nə-</i> D	𐌷 ¹⁴⁵² <i>nja</i> ¹ D
II	<i>wo-</i> US	<i>kɻ-</i> E	<i>kə-</i> CF	<i>gə-</i> US	<i>kə-</i> US	<i>gɐ-</i> US	<i>gæ-</i> US	<i>gə-</i> W	𐌷 ¹³²⁶ <i>kji</i> ¹ IN
	<i>nə-</i> DS	<i>nu-</i> W	<i>nə-</i> CP	<i>ɣə-</i> DS	<i>ɣə-</i> DS	<i>ko-</i> DS	<i>wə-</i> DS	<i>ɣə-</i> E	𐌷 ²⁵⁹⁰ <i>wji</i> ² OUT
		<i>lɻ-</i> US	<i>læ-</i> US					<i>ldə-</i> US	
		<i>tʰu-</i> DS	<i>və-</i> DS					<i>və-</i> DS	
III				<i>də-</i> UNSP	<i>tə-</i> UNSP	<i>dɐ-</i> UNSP	<i>dæ-</i> UNSP		𐌷 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja</i> ² TSL
									𐌷 ⁰⁸⁰⁴ <i>dji</i> ² CSL
IV		<i>rə-</i> UNSP	<i>(də-</i> UNSP	<i>tə-</i> UNSP	<i>dɐ-</i> UNSP	<i>dæ-</i> UNSP)			𐌷 ⁰⁷⁹⁵ <i>rji</i> ² UNSP

In Bragbar, Japhug (East Gyalrongic) and Khroskyabs (West Gyalrongic), the prefixes *kV-* (Bragbar *wo-* being lenited from a former **ko-*, Zhang 2020: 468) and *nV-* are paired together in Axis II. Since this pairing of *kV-* and *nV-* is found across East and West Gyalrongic, it suggests a retention that the opposition between these two prefixes goes back to Proto-Gyalrongic (Zhang 2023b: 211).

Horpa dialects and Tangut both exhibit a prefix *ɣV-* to pair with *kV-*, the latter prefix is cognate with the *kV-* prefix found in East Gyalrongic and Khroskyabs (West Gyalrongic). This suggests that Proto-Gyalrongic orientation prefix *kV-* was inherited in Tangut and Horpa, with a new pairing with *ɣV-*.²² The new pairing can be regarded as a positive shared innovation between Horpa and Tangut, thus validating their classification under the same node.²³

²¹ A few comments are provided for our comparison in Table 7. In Axis I, Existing data suggest an approximate East-West Gyalrongic division. East Gyalrongic employs a dental prefix: Japhug *ɬɻ-*, Bragbar *rv-* (< **to-*, Zhang 2020: 468). In some West Gyalrongic languages, a vocalic prefix for “upward” is present: Khroskyabs *o-*, G.yurong *ə-*, Tangut 𐌷⁵⁹⁸¹ *a*²-. It is possible that the dental upward prefix *rə-* in Geshiza, Bawang and Mazur Stau could be due to initial lenition of the dental *tV-* prefix as attested in East Gyalrongic (Zhang 2020: 489; 2023b: 211), as well as in Qiangic languages (Shirai 2020). Traces of this dental upward prefix are found in the derived secondary nominal form “upward direction” in Khroskyabs varieties, *áru* in Guanyinqiao, *carə* in Siyuewu, and *χurü* in Wobzi. In Axis III, the dental unspecified orientation prefixes in Horpa languages are cognate with Tangut translocative 𐌷⁴³⁴² *dja*²-. However, in terms of paradigmatic structure, Horpa dental unspecified prefixes and the Tangut 𐌷²⁵¹¹ *rji*²- belong to the same semantic category.

²² Most Modern Horpa varieties exhibit a voiced *gV-* for *kV-*. The voicing discrepancy here still requires further investigation.

²³ Tangut 𐌷²⁵⁹⁰ *wji*² ‘outward’ can correspond either to the *ɣV-* prefixes in Horpa-lects, or to *və-* ‘downstream’ in Phosul (Horpa) and *və-* ‘downstream’ in Khroskyabs. Both etymologies regularly derive 𐌷²⁵⁹⁰ *wji*² in Tangut. It is likely that Tangut dropped one of them, or merged them as an ‘outward, centrifugal’ prefix. Sound changes leading to confusion of orientation prefixes is also found with Bragbar *rv-* ‘up’, which could have originated from Proto-Situ **to-* ‘up’ and **ro-* ‘uphill, inclined up’ (Zhang 2020: 470). In addition, The Choyul language also attests the pairing of *kV-* and *ɣV-* (Zheng 2017: 45), suggesting that Choyul could also form a group with Horpa and Tangut. Choyul itself is close to Horpa in many respects in addition to its geographical proximity, and its affiliation deserves further investigation.

4.2.4. Lexicalisation of orientation prefixes

Orientation prefixes constitute an essential part of TAME morphology in Gyalrongic languages. However, experts in both Tangut and modern Gyalrongic all noticed the complexity in terms of the distribution of orientation prefixes in the TAME morphology (Kepping 1982, Nishida 1986, Jacques 2008: 251, Sun 2003: 496, see also Shirai 2009 for similar phenomenon in nDrapa).

In some TAME categories, especially in perfective, there is a certain degree of flexibility for the host verb for choosing a particular orientation prefix, the phenomenon is named verbal “orientability” in the literature (Jacques 2021; Zhang 2020, Accepted). With motion verbs, the selection of orientation prefixes is transparent: one selects the prefix denoting the direction of the motion event. With non-motion verbs, the combinations between orientation prefixes and host verbs are mostly lexicalised, unpredictable, and the orientation prefix encodes opaque spatial values.²⁴ For lexicalisation of orientation prefixes, to cite two prominent examples, in Khroskyabs, *ndzədzáv* ‘to fall’ selects the orientation prefix *o-* ‘upward’ to form its past tense despite the common sense that things fall downward, and *rəz* ‘to say’ selects *kə-* ‘centripetal’, even though “say out” would sound more normal in English and in Chinese. In brief, lexicalisation of orientation prefixes can be understood as the reflex of the inherited semantic classification of verbs.

Lexicalisation reflect a historically more stable use of the orientation prefixes (Gong 2018, Zhang 2023b: 209). The selection of orientation prefixes is unpredictable and random, the odds are low that cognate verbs across sister languages separately select the same orientation prefix. Thus, the selection of orientation prefixes of non-motion verbs is indicative of genetic relation, a method first applied to East Gyalrongic data by Gong (2018: 287-288).

Zhang (to appear in 2024, accepted) noticed innovations in the selection of orientation prefixes in Tangut. In particular, the verbs 𐰇⁴²²⁵ *sja*¹ ‘to kill’ and 𐰇³⁰⁷² *sj*² ‘to die’ are encoded with the same prefix 𐰇⁴³⁴² *dja*² ‘translocative’. This syncretism is uniquely shared by Horpa-lects. In Khroskyabs and East Gyalrongic languages, the two cognate verbs lexicalise different prefixes. As is clearly shown in Table 8,²⁵ there is an innovative merger of lexical orientations for the verb ‘to kill’ and ‘to die’ in Tangut and Horpa, while Khroskyabs and East Gyalrongic retain the distinction by assigning ‘downward’ to ‘to kill’, and ‘centrifugal’ to ‘to die’. It should be mentioned that the use of Geshiza *dæ-* in Table 8 may be due to analogy, as Geshiza generalised the prefix as a standard perfective (Honkasalo 2019: 545). However, Mazur and Bra’go did not undergo such generalisation, and they both employ the cognate prefix *tə-*, forming a strong argument for a shared innovation between Horpa and Tangut.

Table 8. Orientation prefix selection for ‘to kill’ and ‘to die’

	Tangut	Geshiza	Mazur	Bra’go	Khroskyabs	Bragbar	Japhug
‘to kill’	𐰇 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja</i> ²	<i>dæ-</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>næ-</i>	<i>na-</i>	<i>pu-</i>
‘to die’	𐰇 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja</i> ²	<i>dæ-</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>nə-</i>	<i>nə-</i>	<i>nu- / pu-</i>

There is no comprehensive study on the lexicalisation of orientation prefixes in Horpa to date, we can only rely on fragmentary data from Horpa grammars. For now, a quick comparison among Tangut, Khroskyabs and Mazur (without generalising a universal perfective) must suffice. Due to the limited information at hand, we have assembled a list of sixteen-cognate-verb sets where lexicalised orientation prefixes are known, see Table 9 (based on Zhang’s (Accepted) summary of Tangut lexical orientation by adding modern Gyalrongic data). When a verb can be prefixed to two orientation markers, we place the more frequently used one, as indicated by available sources,²⁶ before the less commonly employed one. The orientation prefix not involved in the comparison are shaded in grey.

Table 9. Lexicalisation of orientation prefixes

Gloss	West Gyalrongic	East Gyalrongic
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²⁴ Gong (2018) coined the term “lexical orientation” to describe these unpredictable and opaque spatial values of orientation prefixes.

²⁵ The Bra’go data come from Tunzhi (2019).

²⁶ The Tangut data are extracted from three texts, *The Grove of Categories* ed. by Shi et al. (1993), *Newly Collected Biographies of Affection and Filial Piety* ed. by Jacques (2007), *The Ode of Monthly Pleasure* ed. by Nishida (1986); Stau data from Gates (2021); Khroskyabs data from Lai (2017); Bragbar data from Zhang (2020); Japhug data from Jacques’ (2015) *Dictionnaire Japhug-chinois-français*.

	Tangut	Prefix	Mazur	Prefix	Khros.	Prefix	Bragbar	Prefix
drink	𐞗 ⁴⁶⁵⁸ <i>ɬji¹</i>	𐞗 ²⁵⁹⁰ <i>wji²</i> / 𐞗 ⁰⁷⁹⁵ <i>rjir²</i>	<i>v-tʰi</i>	<i>ɣə-</i>	<i>tʰé</i>	<i>nə-</i>		
pour	𐞗 ⁰⁷³¹ <i>lju²</i>	𐞗 ¹³²⁶ <i>kji¹</i>	<i>ru</i>	<i>kə-</i>	<i>dú</i>	<i>næ-</i>		
die	𐞗 ³⁰⁷² <i>sji²</i>	𐞗 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja²</i>	<i>sɛ</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>sô</i>	<i>nə-</i>	<i>ɛi</i>	<i>nə-</i>
kill	𐞗 ⁴²²⁵ <i>sja¹</i>	𐞗 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja²</i>	<i>v-sɛ</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>sâd</i>	<i>næ-</i>	<i>siét</i>	<i>na-</i>
feed	𐞗 ⁴⁵⁸² <i>tji¹</i>	𐞗 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja²</i>	<i>stʰi</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>stʰé</i>	<i>nə-</i>		
say	𐞗 ¹²⁷⁸ <i>ji²</i>	𐞗 ¹³²⁶ <i>kji¹</i> / 𐞗 ⁰⁷⁹⁵ <i>rjir²</i>	<i>jə</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>jú</i>	<i>o-</i>	<i>rjô</i>	<i>rɐ-</i>
give	𐞗 ¹¹⁰⁵ <i>kʰjow¹</i>	𐞗 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja²</i> / 𐞗 ⁰⁷⁹⁵ <i>rjir²</i>	<i>kʰo</i>	<i>tə- / ɣə-</i>	<i>kʰâ</i>	<i>kə-</i>	<i>kʰáp</i>	<i>nə-</i>
buy	𐞗 ⁵⁸⁴⁵ <i>hwə²</i>	𐞗 ¹³²⁶ <i>kji¹</i>	<i>ru</i>	<i>kə-</i>	<i>ɣdô</i>	<i>kə-</i>		
teach	𐞗 ¹⁰⁸⁷ <i>dzjij²</i>	𐞗 ¹³²⁶ <i>kji¹</i>	<i>ɣzi</i>	<i>kə- / tə-</i>	<i>ldzé</i>	<i>kə-</i>		
wear	𐞗 ⁴⁹⁰⁶ <i>gjiw²</i>	𐞗 ⁵⁹⁸¹ <i>a²</i>	<i>gə</i>	<i>rə-</i>	<i>gi</i>	<i>o-</i>	<i>wiét</i>	<i>rɐ-</i>
ask	𐞗 ⁰²⁶⁸ <i>jir¹</i>	𐞗 ⁴³⁴² <i>dja²</i>	<i>rje</i>	<i>kə-</i>	<i>gi</i>	<i>o-</i>		
write	𐞗 ¹⁷¹⁵ <i>rjar¹</i>	𐞗 ¹⁴⁵² <i>nja¹</i>	<i>v-ræ</i>	<i>kə-</i>	<i>ɣyéd</i>	<i>kə-</i>	<i>rɣt</i> (Japhug)	<i>pu-</i>
break	𐞗 ⁵³⁹⁰ <i>pʰie²</i>	𐞗 ²⁵⁹⁰ <i>wji²</i>	<i>pʰrɛ</i>	<i>nə-</i>	<i>pʰrê</i>	<i>nə-</i>	<i>prê</i>	<i>nə-</i>
know	𐞗 ³⁵⁷⁴ <i>tsjij¹</i>	𐞗 ⁵⁹⁸¹ <i>a²</i>	<i>si</i>	N/A	<i>tsʰé</i>	<i>o-</i>	<i>ɛô</i>	<i>na-</i>
steal	𐞗 ⁵⁸¹⁷ <i>kjwir¹</i>	𐞗 ⁰⁸⁰⁴ <i>dji²</i>	<i>rku</i>	<i>tə-</i>	<i>fkô</i>	<i>næ-</i>		
stand	𐞗 ⁵⁷⁵⁵ <i>jar¹</i>	𐞗 ²⁵⁹⁰ <i>wji²</i>	<i>rje</i>	<i>tə- / kə-</i>	<i>rôz</i>	<i>o-</i>	<i>rjép</i>	<i>rɐ-</i>

Innovations in lexical orientation are considered parallel to those in the orientation paradigm (Section 4.2.3). It is important to note that when an orientation paradigm undergoes morpheme replacement, the new morpheme can also cover the distribution of the original one, encompassing the semantic categories encoded by the old morpheme. A typical example concerns the Japhug prefix *pu-* for “downward”, which resulted from a recent grammaticalisation of *u-pa* ‘bottom’, replacing the original nasal downward prefix (Jacques 2008: 245). With this morpheme replacement, *pu-* covers the semantic domain of the original nasal “downward” prefix, including the encoding of the lexical orientations of verbs to which the nasal prefix was originally assigned (see Table 8).

Therefore, the comparison of lexical orientation in Table 9 focuses more on the semantic categories reflected by orientation prefixes. For example, in the cognate set ‘to say’, Tangut prefix 𐞗⁰⁷⁹⁵ *rjir²* and Mazur’s *tə-* are treated as representing the same semantic category, both reflecting the spatial axis of the unspecified orientation despite unrelated etymologies (see Table 7). Similarly, in the cognate set of the verb ‘to wear’, the vocalic prefixes *o-* in Khroskyabs, 𐞗⁵⁹⁸¹ *a²* in Tangut, and the dental prefixes *rə-* in Geshiza, *rɐ-* in Bragbar are also treated as representing the same semantic category, all unambiguously reflecting semantic category of ‘upward’ in their orientation paradigm.

The comparison of lexical orientation in Table 9 is divided into five types, separated by horizontal lines. The five parts are summarised in Table 10, focusing on West Gyalrongic for now.

Table 10. Summary of lexicalised orientation prefixes

Type	Comparison	Count
Type 1	Tangut = Mazur ≠ Khroskyabs	7
Type 2	Tangut = Mazur = Khroskyabs	3
Type 3	Tangut ≠ (Mazur = Khroskyabs)	3
Type 4	Tangut = Khroskyabs ≠ Mazur	1
Type 5	Tangut ≠ Mazur ≠ Khroskyabs	2

In Type 1, Tangut’s prefixes correspond to the Mazur ones, while excluding the Khroskyabs prefixes. It is worth noting that the Khroskyabs prefixes correspond to Bragbar’s, whenever we find a cognate. Bragbar being a confirmed East Gyalrongic language, the consistent use of prefixes between Khroskyabs and Bragbar must be a retention, which in turns demonstrates that the cases in Tangut and Mazur are shared innovations.

Type 2 illustrates cases of shared retention in lexical orientation across Gyalrongic.

Type 3 shows consistencies between Khroskyabs and Mazur, excluding Tangut. There are two cases, ‘to write’ and ‘to break’, which reflect retention, as East Gyalrongic languages also shows the same prefix with Mazur and Khroskyabs.

Type 4 involves the only case where Khroskyabs is consistent with Tangut, but not with Mazur. As there is one single example, this part is statistically insignificant.

Tangut and Mazur presents a significant number of shared innovations in terms of lexicalisation of orientation prefixes, which means they should be classified under the same branch.

We may pursue additional research on this issue when we have more comprehensive data, which could either corroborate or challenge the tendency evidenced by the current data. However, the primary aim of this section is to present a plausible tract for investigating genetic relationships through orientation prefixes within Gyalrongic.

5. Conclusion

Sino-Tibetan historical linguistics, encompassing reconstruction and subgrouping, has posed a longstanding challenge for historical linguists from its inception (Meillet 1914). To date, a consensus on the applicability of the Neogrammarian method to this huge language family with great internal typological diversity has not been reached, even though fragmentary work has been continuously published along with the increase in detailed descriptions and analyses. This paper selects Tangut and modern Gyalrongic as an example to show how to implement the principles of *Ausnahmslosigkeit* and shared innovation to determine the genetic relationship within a branch with both conservative and eroded varieties.

The classification of Tangut is a litmus test for the Neogrammarian method. On the surface, Tangut appears to share noticeable similarities with Horpa languages, hinting at a potential subgrouping. However, establishing this affiliation remains a formidable challenge at this stage due to our limited understanding of this mediaeval language and the lack of comprehensive investigations on Horpa. Consequently, there is a prevailing tendency to overlook methodological rigour in classifying Tangut, which is in dire need of scrutiny.

This paper tackles this issue by distinguishing between superficial similarities, trivial distributional resemblances, and negative innovations, as opposed to positive shared innovations. It also consolidates plausible tracks for the historical comparison between Tangut and modern Gyalrongic languages, offering detailed commentary and additional data. Notably, we provided a list of linguistically grounded shared phonological and morphological innovations between Tangut and Modern Horpa, offering scientifically rigorous insights into their genetic relationship. Although these analyses might require adjustment in light of new data, we believe that the methodology outlined in this paper sets a promising course for exploring both Tangut grammar, its affiliation, and the genetic reconstruction with the Sino-Tibetan context.

Abbreviations

We follow the Leipzig Glossing Rules. Additional abbreviations are listed as follows: concsv: concessive, DIR: directional, HES: hesitation, IFR: inferential, LNK: linker, MOD: modal discourse enclitic, OPT: optative, TSL: translocative.

References

- Arakawa, Shintarō. 2010. 西夏語の格標識について Seika-go no kakuhyōshiki ni tsuite [on the Tangut case markers]. In Sawada, Hideo (ed.), チベット=ビルマ系言語の文法現象 1: 格とその周辺 *Chibetto = Biruma-kei gengo no bunpō genshō 1: Kaku to sono shūhen* [Grammatical Phenomena of Tibeto-Burman Languages 1: Case-marking and Related Matters], 153–174. Tokyo: 東京外国語大学 アジア・アフリカ言語文化研究所 The Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa, Tokyo University of Foreign Studies.
- Arakawa, Shintaro. 2012. On the Tangut verb prefixes in *Tiansheng Code*. In Popova, Irina (ed.), *Tanguts in Central Asia: a collection of articles marking the 80th anniversary of Prof. E. I. Kuchanov Тангуты в Центральной Азии: сборник статей в честь 80-летия проф. Е.И.Кычанова*, 58–71. Moscow: Oriental Literature.
- Baxter, William H. & Laurent Sagart. 2014. *Old Chinese: A new reconstruction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Beaudouin, Mathieu. 2021. Localiser en tangoute: entre continuums et bipartitions. *Bulletin de la Société de Linguistique de Paris* 116(1). 327–346.
- Beaudouin, Mathieu. 2023. Tangut and Horpa languages: Some shared morphosyntactic features. *Language and Linguistics* 24(4). 611–673.

- Campbell, Lyle & Mauricio J. Mixco. 2007. *Glossary of historical linguistics*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
- Chang, Pei-Chi. 2004. 西夏語的體範疇 Xīxià yǔ de tǐ fānchóu [Aspect in Tangut]. In Yang, Hsiu-Fang, Fang-Min Hsu, Chun-Chih Lee, Dah-an Ho, Jackson T-S Sun & Ying-chin Lin (eds.), *Studies on Sino-Tibetan languages : papers in honor of Professor Hwang-Cherng Gong on his seventieth birthday*, 403–450. Academia Sinica.
- Chang, Pei-Chi. 2020. 論西夏語動詞第二類趨向前綴 Lùn xīxià yǔ dòngcí dì'èr lèi qūxiàng qiánzhuì [On the second type of verbal directional prefix in Tangut]. 西夏學 [Tangutology] (19). 116–144.
- Chirkova, Katia. 2014. The Duoxu language and the Ersu-Lizu-Duoxu relationship. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37(1). 104–146.
- Chirkova, Katia & Zev Handel. 2019. “Brightening” in Ersu, Lizu, Duoxu and neighboring languages. Paper presented at the 5th Workshop on Sino-Tibetan Languages of Southwest China (STLS-2019).
- Clackson, James. 2022. *Methodology in linguistic subgrouping*, 18–32. Cambridge University Press.
- DeLancey, Scott. 2014. Second person verb forms in Tibeto-Burman. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37(1). 3–33.
- DeLancey, Scott. 2021. Classifying Trans-Himalayan (Sino-Tibetan) languages. In Sidwell, Paul & Mathias Jenny (eds.), *The Languages and Linguistics of Mainland Southeast Asia: A Comprehensive Guide*, 207–224. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Downer, GB. 1959. Derivation by tone-change in Classical Chinese. *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 22(02). 258–290.
- Duo'erji. 1998. 道孚语格什扎话研究 Dàofú yǔ Géshízhā huà yánjiū [A study on the Geshiza dialect of Stau]. Beijing: 中国藏学出版社 China Tibetology Publishing House.
- Gates, Jesse P. 2021. A grammar of Mazur Stau. Paris: Écoles des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales dissertation.
- Gates, Jesse P, Sami Honkasalo & Yunfan Lai. 2022. From transitive to intransitive and voiceless to voiced in Proto-Sino-Tibetan: New evidence from Stau, Geshiza, and Khroskyabs. *Language and Linguistics* 23(2). 212–239.
- Gong, Hwang-cherng. 1993. 西夏語的音韻轉換與構詞法 Xīxià yǔ de yīnyùnzhuǎnhuàn yǔ gòucífǎ [Rime alternation and word formation in Tangut]. *Bulletin of the Institute of History and Philology* 64.4. 935–968.
- Gong, Hwang-cherng. 1999. 西夏語的緊元音及其起源 Xīxià yǔ de jǐnyuányīn jí qí qǐyuán [Tense vowels in Tangut and their origins]. *Bulletin of the Institute of History and Philology* 70.2. 531–558.
- Gong, Xun. 2017. Verb stems in Tangut and their orthography. *Scripta* (9). 29–48.
- Gong, Xun. 2018. *Le rgyalrong zbu, une langue tibéto-birmane de Chine du Sud-ouest : Une étude descriptive, typologique et comparative*. Paris: Institut National des Langues et Civilisations Orientales dissertation.
- Gong, Xun. 2021. Nasal preinitials in Tangut Phonology. *Archiv orientální* 89(3). 443–482.
- Gray, Russell D. & Quentin D. Atkinson. 2003. Language-tree divergence times support the Anatolian theory of Indo-European origin. *Nature* 426. 435–439.
- Greenhill, Simon J, Paul Heggarty & Russell D Gray. 2020. Bayesian phylolinguistics. *The handbook of historical linguistics* 2. 226–253.
- Hetzron, Robert. 1976. Two principles of genetic reconstruction. *Lingua* 38(2). 89–108.
- Hill, Nathan W. 2022. Two notes on proto-ersuic. *Cahiers de Linguistique Asie Orientale* 51(1). 105–114.
- Honkasalo, Sami. 2019. A grammar of Eastern Geshiza. Doctoral Dissertation, University of Helsinki.

- Huang, Bufan & Qingxia Dai (eds.). 1992. 藏缅语族语言词汇 *Zàngmiǎnyǔzú yǔyán cíhuì* [Vocabulary in Tibeto-Burman]. Beijing: Minzu University of China.
- Huang, Bufan & Facheng Zhou. 2007. 羌语研究 *qiāngyǔ yánjiū* A study on Qiang. Chengdu: 四川民族出版社 Sichuan Nationalities Publishing House.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2007. *Textes tangoutes I, Nouveau recueil sur l'amour parental et la piété filiale*. Languages of the World/Text Collections 25. München: Lincom Europa.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2008. 嘉絨語研究 *Jiāróngyǔ yánjiū* [Study on the Rgyalrong language]. Beijing: 民族出版社 Nationalities Press.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2009. The Origin of Vowel Alternations in the Tangut Verb. *Language and Linguistics* 10.1. 17–28.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2011. The Structure of the Tangut Verb. *Journal of Chinese Linguistics* 39.2. 419–441.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2012. Agreement morphology: the case of Rgyalrongic and Kiranti. *Language and Linguistics* 13.1. 83–116.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2014. *Esquisse de phonologie et de morphologie historique du tangoute*. Leiden: Brill.
- Jacques, Guillaume (ed.). 2015. *Dictionnaire Japhug-Chinois-Français*. Paris: Projet HimalCo.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2021. *A grammar of Japhug*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Jacques, Guillaume, Yunfan Lai, Anton Antonov & Lobsang Nima. 2017. Stau (Ergong, Horpa). In Thurgood, Graham & Randy LaPolla (eds.), *The Sino-Tibetan Languages*, 597–613. 2nd edn, Abingdon and New York: Routledge.
- Jacques, Guillaume & Thomas Pellard. 2021. Phylogenies based on lexical innovations refute the rung hypothesis. *Diachronica* 38(1). 1–24.
- Kepping, Ksenija B. 1982. Deictic motion verbs in Tangut. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 6(2). 77–82.
- Kepping, Ksenija B. 1984. 唐古特语表示动作方向的范畴 *Tánggütèyǔ biǎoshì dòngzuò fāngxiàng de fānchóu*. 语言研究 [Studies in Language and Linguistics] 2. 215–222.
- Kepping, Ksenija B. 1985. *Тангутский язык – морфология (Tangutskiy jazyk)* [Tangut language]. Moscow: Наука (Nauka).
- Kychanov, Jevgenij Ivanovich. 1974. *Вновь собранные драгоценные парные изречения (Vnov' sobrannye dragocennye parnye izrechenija)* [Newly Collected Precious Paired Sayings]. Moscow : Наука (Nauka).
- Lai, Yunfan. 2015. The Person agreement system of Wobzi Lavrung (rGyalrongic, Tibeto-Burman). *Transactions of the Philological Society* 113(3). 271–285.
- Lai, Yunfan. 2017. *Grammaire du khroskyabs de Wobzi*. Paris: Université Sorbonne Nouvelle (Paris 3) dissertation.
- Lai, Yunfan. 2020. The historical development of inverse marking in Khroskyabs: Evidence from two modern varieties: Siyuewu and Wobzi. *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 83(2). 259–281.
- Lai, Yunfan. 2021. 嘉絨语组语言动词的分类 —— 以绰斯甲(拉坞戎)语为例 *Jiāróngyǔzǔ yǔyán dòngcí de fēnlèi — yǐ Chuòsījiǎ (Lāwùróng) yǔ wéili* [The classification of verbs in Rgyalrongic languages, from a Khroskyabs perspective]. 语言学论丛 [Essays on linguistics] 63. 68–95.

- Lai, Yunfan. 2022. When internal reconstruction goes further: Proposing the vowel system of Proto-Khroskyabs through examining bound state apophony. *Folia Linguistica Historica* 56(s43-s1). 213–261.
- Lai, Yunfan. 2023. On plosive-nasal correspondences and alternations in Gyalrongic and their possible solutions. *Cahiers de Linguistique Asie Orientale* 52(1). 1 – 39. https://brill.com/view/journals/clao/52/1/article-p1_1.xml.
- Lai, Yunfan. to appear. Mutual predictiveness of sound correspondences hints at reconstruction and language subgrouping: The case of Gyalrongic preinitials. *Diachronica* 41(5).
- Lai, Yunfan. to appear in 2025. Long vowels and the origin of stem alternation in Khroskyabs. *Bulletin of Chinese Linguistics (A Collection of Essays by 2022 Outstanding Young Scholars of the Li Fang-Kuei Society)*.
- Lai, Yunfan, Xun Gong, Jesse P. Gates & Guillaume Jacques. 2020. Tangut as a West Gyalrongic language. *Folia Linguistica Historica* 41(1). 171–203.
- Lai, Yunfan & Johann-Mattis List. 2023. Lexical data for the historical comparison of Rgyalrongic languages. *Open Research Europe* (3). 99.
- LaPolla, Randy J. 1992. ‘Anti-ergative’ marking in Tibeto-Burman. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 15(1). 1–9.
- Laufer, Berthold. 1916. The Si-Hia language, a study in Indo-Chinese philology. *T'oung Pao* 17(1). 1–126.
- Leskien, August. 1876. *Die Declination im Slavisch-Litauischen und Germanischen*. Leipzig: Hirzel.
- Li, Fanwen & Xiangrong Lin. 1983. 試論嘉戎語與道孚語的關係 – 兼論西夏語與道孚語、嘉戎語、藏語的關係 Shìlùn Jiāróngyǔ yǔ Dàofúyǔ de guānxì – Jiānlùn Xīxiàyǔ yǔ Dàofúyǔ, Jiāróngyǔ, Zàngyǔ de guānxì [An exploration of the relationship between Gyalrong and Stau Languages – Along with a Discussion on the relationship between Tangut, Stau, Gyalrong, and Tibetan]. In 西夏研究論集 [Collection of Tangut Studies], 279–305. Ningxia Renmin Chubanshe.
- Lin, Ying-chin. 1987. 孫子兵法西夏譯本中所見動詞詞頭的語法功能 Sūnzibīngfǎ Xīxià yìběn zhōng suǒjiàn dòngcí cítóu de yǔfǎ gōngnéng [The grammatical functions of verbal prefixed observed in the Tangut version of *Sunzibingfa*]. *Bulletin of the Institute of History and Philology* 歷史語言研究所集刊 2. 381–445.
- Lin, You-Jing. 2003. Tense and Aspect Morphology in the Zhuokeji rGyalrong Verb. *Cahiers de Linguistique - Asie Orientale* 32.2. 245–286.
- List, Johann-Mattis, Simon J Greenhill & Russell D Gray. 2017. The potential of automatic word comparison for historical linguistics. *PloS one* 12(1). e0170046.
- Matisoff, James A. 2004. “Brightening” and the place of Xixia in the Qiangic branch of Tibeto-Burman. In Lin, Ying-chin, Fang-min Hsu, Chun-chih Lee, Jackson T.-S. Sun, Hsiu-fang Yang & Dah-an Ho (eds.), *Studies on Sino-Tibetan Languages: Papers in Honor of Professor Hwang-Cherng Gong on His Seventieth Birthday*. Taipei: Institute of Linguistics, Academia Sinica.
- Meelen, Marieke, Nathan W Hill & Hannes Fellner. 2022. What are cognates? *Papers in Historical Phonology* 7. 44–80.
- Meillet, Antoine. 1914. Le problème de la parenté des langues .
- Nishida, Tatsuo. 1976. Hsihsia, Tosu and Lolo-Burmese languages. *Studia phonologica* (10). 1–15.
- Nishida, Tatsuo. 1986. 西夏語『月々樂詩』の研究 Seika-go “Getsu gestu raku shi” no kenkyū [Research on the Tangut Ode on Monthly Pleasures]. 京都大學文學部研究紀要 *Memoirs of the Department of Literature, Kyoto University* 25. 1–116.

- Nishida, Tatsuo. 1989 [2012]. 西夏語 Seikago [Tangut]. In 言語学大辞典 *Gengogaku Daijiten* [The Sanseido Encyclopedia of Linguistics], vol. 2, 408–429. Tokyo: Sanseido.
- Osthoff, Hermann & Karl Brugmann. 1878. *Morphologische untersuchungen auf dem gebiete der indogermanischen sprachen*. Leipzig: S. Hirzel.
- Pfeifer, Wolfgang. 1993. Digitalisierte und von Wolfgang Pfeifer überarbeitete Version im digitalen Wörterbuch der deutschen Sprache. <https://www.dwds.de/wb/etymwb/holen>, accessed 05/05/2024.
- Prins, Marielle. 2017. *A Grammar of rGyalrong, Jiāomùzú (Kiom-kyo) Dialects: A Wen of Relations*. Brill.
- Qu, Aitang & Jingsong. 2007. 嘉戎语上寨话 Jiāróngyǔ Shàngzhàihuà [The Stod.sde dialect of Gyalrong]. 民族语文 [Minority languages of China] 5. 70–81.
- Sagart, Laurent, Guillaume Jacques, Yunfan Lai, Robin J. Ryder, Valentin Thouzeau, Simon J. Greenhill & Johann-Mattis List. 2019. Dated language phylogenies shed light on the ancestry of Sino-Tibetan. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116(21). 10317–10322. <https://www.pnas.org/content/116/21/10317.full.pdf> (accessed 11 May 2020).
- Schleicher, August. 1853. Die ersten spaltungen des indogermanischen urvolkes. *Allgemeine Monatsschrift für Wissenschaft und Literatur* 3. 786–787.
- Shi, Jinbo, Zhenhua Huang & Hongyin Nie. 1993. 類林研究 *Lèi lín yánjiū* [A study on “the Grove of Categories”]. Yinchuan: 寧夏人民出版社 [People's publishing house of Ningxia].
- Shirai, Satoko. 2009. Directional prefixes in nDrapa and neighboring languages: An areal feature of Western Sichuan. *Senri Ethnological Studies* 75. 7–20.
- Shirai, Satoko. 2020. A geolinguistic study of directional prefixes in the Qiangic language area. *Himalayan Linguistics* 19(1). 365–392.
- Stein, Rolf A. 1966. Nouveaux documents tibétains sur le Mi-Ñag/Si-Hia. In *Mélanges de sinologie offerts à Monsieur Paul Demiéville I*, 281–289. Paris: Presses Universitaires de France.
- Sun, Hongkai. 1991. 从词汇比较看西夏语与藏缅语族羌语支的关系 *Cóng cíhuìbǐjiào kàn Xīxià yǔ yǔ Zàngmiǎnyǔzú Qiāngyǔzhī de guānxì* [Relationship between Xixia and the Qiangic branch in Tibeto-Burman family through vocabulary comparison]. 民族语文 [Monority languages of China] 2(1). 1–11.
- Sun, Hongkai. 2001. 論藏緬語族中的羌語支語言 *Lùn Zàngmiǎnyǔzú zhōng de Qiāng yǔ zhī yǔyán* [On language of the Qiangic branch in Tibeto-Burman]. *Language and Linguistics* 2(1). 157–181.
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. 2000a. Parallelisms in the verb morphology of Sidaba rGyalrong and Lavrung in rGyalrongic. *Language and Linguistics* 1(1). 161–190.
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. 2000b. Stem alternations in Puxi verb inflection: Toward validating the rGyalrongic subgroup in Qiangic. *Language and Linguistics* 1(2). 211–232.
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. 2003. Caodeng rGyalrong. In Thurgood, Graham & Randy LaPolla (eds.), *The Sino-Tibetan languages*, 490–502. London: Routledge.
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. 2007. Morphological Causative Formation in Shangzhai Horpa. *Bulletin of Chinese Linguistics* 2(1). 211–232.
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. 2023. Gser-rdo: A new Tibetic language across the rNgaba-dKarmdzes border. *Language and Linguistics* 24(2). 345–390.
- Trask, Robert Lawrence. 2000. *The dictionary of historical and comparative linguistics*. Psychology Press.
- Tunzhi. 2019. *Outline of Bra'go variety of rTa'u (Horpa)*. Melbourne: La Trobe University disseration.
- Wolfenden, Stuart N. 1931. On the Tibetan transcriptions of Si-Hia words. *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 63(1). 47–52.

- Yang, Chih-Fan. 2021. The morpho-syntax of tense, aspect, evidentiality and modality in Bawang Horpa. Doctoral Dissertation, National Taiwan Normal University.
- Yin, Weibin. 2007. 业隆拉坞戎语研究 Yèlóng Lāwūróngyǔ Yánjiū [Study on the 'Jorogs Lavrung language]. Beijing: 民族出版社 Nationalities Press.
- Zàngmiǎnyǔ Yǔyīn hé Cíhuì Biānxiězǔ (ed.). 1992. 藏缅语语音和词汇 Zàngmiǎnyǔ yǔyīn hé cíhuì [Phonology and vocabulary of Tibeto-Burman languages]. Beijing: 中国社会科学出版社 [China Social Sciences Press].
- Zhang, Menghan, Shi Yan, Wuyun Pan & Li Jin. 2019. Phylogenetic evidence for Sino-Tibetan origin in Northern China in the Late Neolithic. *Nature* 569(7754). 112–115. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-019-1153-z>.
- Zhang, Shuya. 2019. From proximate/obviative to number marking: Reanalysis of hierarchical indexation in Rgyalrong languages. *Journal of Chinese Linguistics* 47(1). 125–150.
- Zhang, Shuya. 2020. Le rgyalrong situ de Brag-bar et sa contribution à la typologie de l'expression des relations spatiales: l'orientation et le mouvement associé. Doctoral Dissertation, Institut National des Langues et Civilisations Orientales.
- Zhang, Shuya. 2022. Rethinking the *-s suffix in Old Chinese: With new evidence from Situ Rgyalrong. *Folia Linguistica* 56(s43-s1). 129–167. <https://doi.org/10.1515/flin-2022-2014>.
- Zhang, Shuya. 2023a. The history of the polyfunctional 𑄎¹¹³⁹ *jij*^l in Tangut: How did the accusative/genitive syncretism come about? *Studies in Language* 47(3). 643–682. <https://www.jbe-platform.com/content/journals/10.1075/sl.21085.zha>.
- Zhang, Shuya. 2023b. Towards a new generalization of the tri-axial orientation system in Situ Rgyalrong. *Transactions of the Philological Society* 121(2). 203–225.
- Zhang, Shuya. to appear in 2024. 论西夏语趋向前缀 𑄎²- 的语法化:完整体与非完整体同形之形成 Lùn Xīxià yǔ qūxiàng qiánzhuì dǎ²- de yǔfǎ huà: wánzhěng tǐ yǔ fēi wánzhěng tǐ tóngxíng zhī xíngchéng [On the grammaticalisation of the directional prefix 𑄎² -: the formation of the perfective and imperfective isomorphism]. 西夏学 [Tangutology] 29 (2): 96–128.
- Zhang, Shuya. accepted. 西夏语趋向前缀与动词的趋向可易性 Xīxià yǔ qūxiàng qiánzhuì yǔ dòngcí de qūxiàng kěyìxìng [Directional prefixes and verbal orientability in Tangut]. *Language and Linguistics*.
- Zhang, Shuya, Guillaume Jacques & Yunfan Lai. 2019. A study of cognates between Gyalrong languages and Old Chinese. *Journal of Language Relationship* 17(1). 73–92. Zhang, Shuya, Guillaume Jacques & Yunfan Lai. 2019c. A study of cognates between Gyalrong languages and Old Chinese. *Journal of Language Relationship* 17(1). 73–92.
- Zheng, Jingyao. 2017. 却域语绒坝话的音系分析 Quèyùyǔ Róngbàhuà de yīnxì fēnxī [A phonological study of Rongpa Choyul]. Beijing: Peking University master's thesis.